

Co-thinking and Creation for STEAM diversity-gap reduction

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UNIT PLAN Descriptions

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Amendment History

Version	Revision	Date	Author	Modification
1	0	14/03/2022	David Fonseca	Initial version. To review by all schools
1	1	14/03/2022	David Fonseca	Errors Review.
1	2	27/04/2022	David Fonseca	Adding new context for the unit plan defined.
1	3	5/05/2022	David Fonseca	Added a new Unit Plan (31)
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2	2	5/12/2022	David Fonseca	Final Version with all Units Plan collected, included and formatted.
2	3	10/03/2023	Alicia García-Holgado	Preparation for publishing as part of the framework

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INSTRUCTIONS

Each Unit plan has the following fields that resume it (please review):

Age Average:								Teaching Hours:					
Subjects	S	T	E	A	M	Others:							

Curricular: Interdisciplinary Instruction (II) / Emphasis on Creativity (EC) // Addresses Diversity Gap (DG)

Diversity GAP: Gender (G), Immigration (I), Economic (E), Religion (R), Disabilities (D), Others (O)

When we talk about diversity, we are concerned about bringing together representative people from all sectors of society, different cultures, disabilities, ethnic groups, gender, or sexual orientation. When the needs of some groups are not adequately addressed, we also speak of inclusion (Lee et al., 2014; Winters, 2013). The low diversity in STEAM studies has been identified as one of the main problems that need to be solved to reduce the diversity gap that exists in these sectors (Conde et al., 2021; García-Holgado et al., 2019; Tsui, 2007).

Curricular	II	EC	DG	Diversity GAP	G	I	E	R	D	Others:	
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Instruction: Active Learning (AL), Project Based Learning (PBL), Personalization of Learning and Inclusive Environment (PLIE), Service Learning (SL), Collaborative Learning (CL), Design Thinking Methodologies (DTM), Inquired Based Learning (IBL), Tinkering (T), Other

Instruction	AL	PBL	PLIE	SL	CL	DTM	IBL	T	Other:		
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1.- Insulated Hut Designing and Building for Street Animals and Building for Street Animals (Saddettin)

Age Average:	10-13	Teaching Hours:	8
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL	PLIE SL CL DTM IBL T	Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn about insulation with the help of new technologies and 3D models. We'll learn about designing insulated houses with the help of tinkering, protecting animals, and creating a shelter environment.

2. Materials/Resources

Computer, insulation materials, sandpaper, glue, utility knife, silicone gun, styrofoam, glass wool, and 3D design programs.

2. a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=b31pupB_yXo
- <https://www.pinterest.fr/pin/497858933778994997/>
- <https://www.teacherspayteachers.com/Product/Animal-Habitat-and-Needs-STEM-activities-4147533>

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about insulation, drawing 3D huts, how to use insulation materials, and animal lovers.
- Ensuring the application and use of insulation materials by students.
- Tinkering a 3D house.
- Building a 3D hut.
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Cooperate positively.
- How to overcome problems.
- How to follow visual instructions.
- How to build and design with constraints such as materials and time.
- How to reflect on their learning.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: Makes 3d drawing of the hut on computer: Student creates a 3D kennel using Sketchup.

- Session 2: Researches and determines insulation materials: First students research insulation materials. Teachers inform about insulation materials. We cooperate as five teachers. (IT, Mats, Science)

- Session 3: Students design the hut model they draw in 3D in real life: Students finish this session in 6 hours.

- Session 4: Students leave the model they prepared in the appropriate environment in nature:

5. Results/Evidence

- 3D Hut model and the real model (photos).
- E-portfolio: digital experience lab book (including photo, video...).

Observations/Personal Notes

We added ARTS to STEM. We created a STEAM lab. Guidance counselor of the school:

- When we consider the developmental stages of our students, being admired and belonging to a group is one of the most important criteria for this period.
- The impression I got from the interviews I had with the children and the teachers shows that the children fulfill the characteristics of this period.
- I observed that these children had a strong motivation while taking part in this study and that the studies caused positive emotions in them.
- When we consider the individual characteristics of the children in the group, I observed that some children's negative emotions turned into positive emotions in such a study.
- After this study, I think that children have positive contributions in terms of teamwork, cooperation, and belonging to a group.

Arts teacher:

In this project, I think that knowledge alone is not enough, team spirit and working together with the team will be beneficial. While we are working on art with our students, we aim to use mathematics and science together and to give this unity to our children. While performing these activities in our school, we are trying to make people comprehend the point of view of art, and the importance of looking, seeing, planning, and being a team. With this project, we understood them better. I think we pass it on to our children better.

2.- Traffic light coding (Saddettin)

Age Average:	10-14	Teaching Hours:	6
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL	DTM IBL T	Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

Traffic light design using Arduino.

2. Materials/Resources

Arduino sets.

3. Learning Objectives

Making circuit setup and coding with basic electrical knowledge.

4. Unit Plan Outline

Students can design traffic lights by combining science and informatics courses with economically disadvantaged groups.

- Session 1: Collects information about the types of connections of electrical circuits.
- Session 2: Determines the advantages and disadvantages of connections.
- Session 3: The student writes the codes by establishing the traffic circuit.

5. Results/Evidence

- Understands the importance of traffic lights. Traffic lights coding with Arduino (photos).
- e-portfolio: digital experience lab book (including photo, video...).

Observations/Personal Notes

3.- Game design with makey makey (Sadettin)

Age Average:	11-14	Teaching Hours:	4
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL	DTM IBL T	Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

Using arrow keys with makey makey.

2. Materials/Resources

Makey makey, scratch.

3. Learning Objectives

Combining coding skills with makey makey.

4. Unit Plan Outline

Students use the arrow keys with makey makey by coding with Scratch.

5. Results/Evidence

Making teamwork with the disadvantaged group and observing that makey makey is run.

Observations/Personal Notes

4.- FRICTIONAL FORCE (Sadettin)

Age Average:	10-14	Teaching Hours:	8
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL	PLIE SL CL	DTM IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

Understanding the frictional force.

2. Materials/Resources

- Marble.
- Sandpaper.
- Wood.
- Model car.
- Ball.
- Cardboard.
- Tile wood.

3. Learning Objectives

Realizes that friction force has the effect of making movement difficult.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: Give examples of friction force from daily life.
- Session 2: explores the effect of friction force on motion in various environments by experimenting.
- Session 3: generates new ideas to increase or decrease friction in daily life.
- Session 4: Designs friction force animation.

5. Results/Evidence

- About friction force animation and mockup materials (photos).
- e-portfolio: digital experience lab book (including photo, video...).

Observations/Personal Notes

5.- Drawing Long Bone Model (Sadettin)

Age Average:	10-14	Teaching Hours:	4
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL	DTM IBL	T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

Learn about how to draw long bone models.

2. Materials/Resources

- Computers.
- 3D design programs.

3. Learning Objectives

- Explores the structure of the long bone and draws its 3d model.
- It prints from a 3D printer.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: collects information about the structure of the long bone.
- Session 2: identifies the parts of the long bone.
- Session 3: draws a 3D model of a long bone.
- Session 4: Prints 3D long bone model.

5. Results/Evidence

- 3D long bone material (photos).
- e-portfolio: digital experience lab book (including photo, video...).

Observations/Personal Notes

6.- Calculating volume with unit cubes (Sadettin)

Age Average:	10-13	Teaching Hours:	8
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL	PLIE SL CL DTM IBL	T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

Understand the concept of volume with unit cubes

2. Materials/Resources

- Carton.
- Glue.
- Scissors.
- Ruler.
- Glue gun.
- Geogebra application.

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=linDZz2l1Z0>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lllj5dxJy4I&t=29s>

3. Learning Objectives

Visual understanding of volume calculation

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: Students visually understand the expansion of the cube with the GeoGebra program.

- Session 2: The students chose one of the cube expansions and combined them from the cube form opened from cardboard and made it closed.

- Session 3: Students created structures with cubes. They tried to find the volume of the structure by counting the cubes.

5. Results/Evidence

- Students learned that cubes have 11 different expansions. They learned that volume can be calculated with cubes. They painted the cubes and integrated them with art. (photos).
- e-portfolio: digital experience lab book (including photo, video...).

Observations/Personal Notes

The students did not know before that the cube has 11 expansions. The students said that they were happy while doing the activities. We did an interdisciplinary study by combining the fields of mathematics and painting. They wanted the event to be longer.

7.- Designing an environmental awareness game with makey makey and planting trees (Sadettin)

Age Average:	10-13	Teaching Hours:	8
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL	PLIE SL CL DTM IBL T	Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

Game design with makey makey about environment awareness.

2. Materials/Resources

- Makey makey.
- Tree Sapling.
- Scratch.

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s0MMUvqri5w>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gyUpuUYG9Fs>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kPYTr0a36aM>

3. Learning Objectives

- Protecting nature and gaining environmental awareness
- Use of makey makey
- Coding

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: Investigates the causes and solutions of environmental pollution. The students researched environmental protection. They reported their results.

- Session 2: Gains awareness of nature protection and environmental protection. Plants trees.

- Session 3: We designed a model by calculating the terracing intervals of the trees.

- Session 4: Design a game with Scratch and makey makey about the environment.

- Session 5: They built the makey makey circuit. They played the game they coded with makey makey. They have gained environmental awareness.

5. Results/Evidence

- Students gained awareness about the environment by using technology. (photos).
- e-portfolio: digital experience lab book (including photo, video...).

Observations/Personal Notes

With an interdisciplinary study, we designed an activity about creating environmental awareness following the main idea of CreaSTEAM. We brought environmental awareness by combining science, mathematics, and technology subjects.

8.- Space Pollution (Bahçeşehir Secondary Okulu)

Age Average:	12-14	Teaching Hours:	2
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL	DTM IBL T	Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

The lesson starts with a video, then some warming/intriguing questions. Groups of 4-5 students search for some basic info about space/space pollution, then create ideas and develop a product, and lastly test the product.

2. Materials/Resources

- Tablets (for student groups for searching).
- Cardboard cups.
- Balloons.
- Colored cardboard.
- Duct tape.
- Mini pompoms.
- Ping pong balls.
- Felts in different colors.
- Wooden pencils.

3. Learning Objectives

- Explains space technologies.
- Expresses the causes of space pollution and predicts the possible consequences of this pollution.
- Explain the relationship between technology and space exploration. Performs addition and subtraction with integers and solves related problems.
- Use the features of aggregation as a strategy for smooth trading.
- The student identifies the processes involved in an engineering project. It explains the stages such as planning, prototyping, design, execution, quality control, and reporting. In the project work, the student assumes himself as a team member in different roles and completes the work required by that role.
- The student prepares picture sketches to develop ideas, solve problems and understand the relationships in the design process. The student lists the steps of the design process and explains the activities done in each part. The student realizes the importance of focusing on details while executing the design process.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Watching a video and two intriguing questions by the teacher.

- Searching /student groups search the topic and learn the definitions of space.
- Students make presentations about their search.
- Brainstorming and creating ideas.
- Developing/designing a product from the materials.
- Testing the product, sharing the experience, and using the prototype.
- Feedback and questions and evaluation.

5. Results/Evidence

- Asking students to answer Kahoot questions prepared by the teacher about the subject. With the help of the system, how many students answered incorrectly and the student with the best score is determined. Thus, at the end of the lesson, an evaluation is made with instant feedback.
- Prepared Kahoot.

Observations/Personal Notes

9.- Tissue Paper Parachute (Bursa Ozel Cagdas Onclu Okulu)

Age Average:	10-11	Teaching Hours:	4
Subjects	S T E A M Others:		
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL	DTM IBL T	Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn about observing the effect of air resistance on the parachute. The students will learn the subject more effectively by making a parachute model. KEY CONCEPTS: Gravity, drag, air resistance.

2. Materials/Resources

- Expandable materials: Tissue paper or a plastic bag.
- Scissors.
- Ruler.
- Tape.
- Hole puncher.
- Twine.
- Small non-breakable action figures or miniature dolls may be dropped on the floor. If you do not have an action figure, use a piece of clay, a small wooden block, a measuring spoon, etc.
- Location to drop your parachute from, e.g. a 2nd-floor window, balcony, open staircase.

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6RA9x4wlnW8>
- <https://www.sciencebuddies.org/stem-activities/parachutes?from=YouTube#summary>
- <https://www.sciencebuddies.org/teacher-resources/lesson-plans/parachutes-forces?from=YouTube#summary>

2 b) Materials/Resources - Documents (optional)

- <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1Umm18qfdqn5zCZ6UO3HT4VbrTm4CIMRU>
- <https://www.sciencebuddies.org/stem-activities/parachutes?from=YouTube#summary>
- <https://www.sciencebuddies.org/teacher-resources/lesson-plans/parachutes-forces?from=YouTube#summary>

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about air resistance, gravity, and drag.
- Develop scientific inquiry skills, by making sense of an experience or answer a question using evidence and scientific understanding.
- Develop practical skills that include good observation, measurement, and equipment handling skills so that learners can collect accurate and reliable data.
- Making a model.
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- In particular, female students' interest in engineering increases.

Background Information for Teachers: This section contains a quick review for teachers of the science and concepts covered in this lesson.

- Scientists refer to a **push** or **pull** as a **force**. Forces can change the movement of an object (its speed and/or direction), but they do not always do so. Imagine a grocery cart standing still. You can push on the handlebar to make it move (Figure 1, top left). If it is already moving, and you push it, you can make it move faster (Figure 1, top right).

Figure 1. Pushing on a shopping cart can change its motion. Red lines indicate the cart's speed, and blue arrows indicate a push. A push can make a cart move (top left), and an additional push can make it speed up (top right). Pushes in opposite directions can cancel each other out (bottom).

- It gets a little more complicated when more than one force acts on an object. Imagine pushing the grocery cart again, but this time, another person is pushing equally hard on the opposite side of the cart. The two opposing forces would cancel each other out, and the cart's movement would not change (Figure 1, bottom). Most often, objects have many forces acting on them. We often do not realize this because some forces are canceled out by others and thus do not affect the motion of the object. For example, the shopping cart has mass, so gravity pulls it down—but the cart does not fall, because the ground pushes back with equal strength in the opposite direction.
- In this lesson, students will study how forces can affect the speed of a falling object by looking at a skydiver. Without an open parachute, the skydiver is in free fall. Gravity pulls him or her down, and almost nothing is pushing back up to slow down or prevent the fall. The situation changes when the parachute opens. Suddenly, a lot of air particles need to move out of the way to let the open parachute pass. The air pushes the parachute—and the skydiver hanging from it—up, as shown in Figure 2. This push, or force, is called **air resistance** or drag. It has a direction opposite to the movement. In this case, this force acts in the opposite direction to gravity. As a result, the force of gravity is partially canceled out and the skydiver does not gain speed as quickly. The skydiver falls at a slower pace and can safely land.

Figure 2. Forces acting on a skydiver coming down with a parachute.

- As shown in Figure 2, scientists represent forces with directional arrows. The arrow points to where the force pulls or pushes. Gravity always pulls objects down, and air resistance always points against the motion of the object it acts upon.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- To make the canopy for the parachute, cut a 30 cm by 30 cm square (12 by 12 inches) out of the tissue paper (or plastic bag), reinforce the corners with tape and punch a hole in each corner.

- Create suspension lines by cutting four strings from the twine, each 30 cm (12 inches) long.

- To assemble your parachute, attach one end of each suspension line to each corner of the tissue paper, fold the canopy in four so its corners lay on top of each other, and knot the unattached ends of the four suspension lines together.

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Bring your parachute and action figure to your test location.
 - ATTENTION: In a moment, you will drop your figure (without the parachute) from this spot. Do you think it will make a soft or hard landing? Can you predict with precision where it will land?
- Drop your figure from the same location several times to see if your predictions were correct.
- Attach the parachute to your figure by winding the knotted end of the suspension lines around the middle of your figure and securing it with a knot or tape.
 - ATTENTION: In a moment, you will drop your figure equipped with a parachute from this spot. How do you think it will land this time? Can you also predict where it will land?
- Fold your canopy in four so its four corners lay on top of each other. Make sure the suspension lines are not tangled. Pick the parachute up from the corner diagonally opposite the corner with the strings. Your figure should now hang under the parachute.
- Drop your figure equipped with a parachute several more times from the same location.
 - ATTENTION: How are these falls different from the falls without a parachute? Why would a parachute create these differences?

- Fold your parachute in four so the corners are stacked. Cut the tip of the corner that is diagonally opposite the corner with the strings attached.
- Open your parachute and see that there is now a hole in the middle of the canopy.
 - ATTENTION: How do you predict this hole in the middle of the parachute will affect the fall?
- Fold your canopy in four again. Pick it up at the corner that has been cut away and drop your figure several times from the same location.
 - ATTENTION: How did the hole change the way the figure falls? Why would this happen?

5. Results/Evidence

- e-portfolio: digital experience lab book (including photo, video...)
- The final product. (parachute)

Observations/Personal Notes

- Students should be given a certain amount of time to design.
- Parachutes made by students should be presented to other groups.
- The materials should be prepared on the table before the event starts.

For Further Exploration:

- Use a timer to measure how long each fall takes. Can you calculate the average speed of your figure during the fall? Which parachute creates the slowest fall?
- Make canopies of different materials, different sizes, and different shapes. Which ones work best?
- Find out how many holes you can create before your parachute no longer functions, or whether or not the location of the hole makes a difference. You could also gradually increase the size of the hole and study how its performance changes.
- Measure the impact of the fall by letting your figure land in a sandbox. How deep is the indent created by the fall?

10.- Marble machines system (Özel Mesafe Mesleki Ve Teknik Anadolu Lisesi)

Age Average:	15-17	Teaching Hours:	7
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity	GAP G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL	PLIE SL	CL DTM IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn to develop and convert circular motion to linear motion, convert kinetic energy to potential energy, and understand the simple machine wheel system. They will also develop their skills in measurement and drawing instructions on AutoCAD. Develop their visualization skills for 3D view. Learning how to use the tool bench, and developing timing, and planning skills.

2. Materials/Resources

- Computers(laptops).
- CNC.
- Saws.
- Hammers.
- Screwdrivers.
- Pliers.
- Drills.
- Wood.
- Carton.
- AutoCAD.

2 b) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7oEdgY6XD2g>
- <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1Umm18qfdqn5zCZ6UO3HT4VbrTm4CIMRU>

3. Learning Objectives

- Mathematics: Learn to measure such as diameter, radius, length, and width for components/materials!
- Science: Learn and develop converting circular motion to linear motion, converting kinetic energy to potential energy, and understanding the simple machine wheel system.
- Art: Using measurement and drawing instructions on AutoCAD. Develop their visualization skills for 3D view. Learning how to use the tool bench, and developing timing, and planning skills.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: Design, and explanation of the activity/product. We will start with a video, (marble machines system)
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Tx2CTNYjrfE>
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7oEdgY6XD2g>
- Session 2: Discussion about students' ideas about how to design this system; Discussion about phases of the product. Discussion about how to integrate the components of thinking and planning about physics and math.
- Session 3: Designing and deciding about the equipment, and decision about main material; WOODEN, checking and preparing materials list and discussing how to use recycled materials
- Session 4: First design draft by handwriting/on paper; After that, design on AutoCAD 2D or 3D. printing the designed drafts and getting ready.

- Session 5: Group working; one group for listing materials for drafts. matching the components of the draft by their materials. Sharing responsibilities.

- Session 6: Creation; Cutting materials, pasting/gluing/sticking materials, and mounting the components.

- Session 7: Share the product (marble machine system) with a short presentation. Evaluation.

5. Results/Evidence

- Marble machine system/material/toy/project physically.
- E-portfolio: digital experience lab plan with photos and videos.

Observations/Personal Notes

I feel happy to see how to use our theory/lesson in practice for our students. I think Our students are very motivated and happy at this lab with this kind of activity.

11.- Clemens for future - How can we make school more sustainable? Mobility as a first focus (Clemens-Brentano)

Age Average:	15-16	Teaching Hours:	14			
Subjects	S	T	E	A	M	Others: Social sciences, politics, geography
Curricular	II	EC	DG	Diversity GAP		G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL	PBL	PLIE	SL	CL	DTM IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

Basic knowledge of sustainability, action planning, and realization of projects especially Installation and design of a mobile phone charging station with solar energy

2. Materials/Resources

- Wood.
- Metal.
- Solar panels.
- Paint colors.
- Paintbrush.
- Printer.
- Construction kit windmill:
 - www.engagement.global.de
 - www.sdgs.un.org
 - www.publicclimateschool.de
 - www.amnesty.de

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

Meine Antwort

3. Learning Objectives

- Problem-solving strategies.
- Collaborative competencies.
- Basic knowledge about coherences between science.
- Politics and human rights.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- What do you understand by sustainability?
- Basic knowledge of sustainability.
- Sustainability in everyday life.
- Research your project:

- Painting the closet for the cell phones.
- Installing the solar module.
- Installation of the doors of the shelf.
- Paint the doors.
- Create an advertisement for the mobile phone charging station.

5. Results/Evidence

Progress on the project: first period: test about knowledge, second period: developing an own project

Observations/Personal Notes

Difficulties: organization of rooms and teachers who have the needed abilities, coordination of teachers and timetable and necessary rooms

Students: students' assistance - some students need support but their problem is school absence so it's difficult to help them students have difficulties understanding the new character of the project, it is also difficult for them to think of possibilities and to create new ideas because they are not used to it

12.- Arduino solutions for everyone (La Salle Congrs)

Age Average:	16-17	Teaching Hours:	12
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL	DTM IBL T	Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

The unit consists of a brief introduction to Arduino and a development of project-based learning to apply Arduino as a solution for problems/challenges.

2. Materials/Resources

- Arduino kit (Arduino, sensors, wires, protoboard...).
- Access to 3D and 2D design software: Tinkercad, Cura, GIMP, Canva, etc.
- Access to 3D printer, vinyl cutter, CNC, and laser engraving.
- Access to cardboard, wood, methacrylate, paints, projector, blackboard, workbench, tools, and others.
- Access to protocols and guidelines.

3. Learning Objectives

- Arduino basics (the first lessons).
- Arduino constructions and code.
- Inclusive thinking.

4. Unit Plan Outline

The plan will take around 12 sessions:

- The plan starts with 3-4 basic lessons about Arduino and how it works (most of the students know something and have previous knowledge about Arduino). For this part, the students will be in pairs. We propose three different practices for this:
 - Make a traffic light,
 - A countdown,
 - And connect the lead controlled by a button.
- After that, for the next 8-9 lessons, the teacher will divide the students into groups of 4-5 students each. Each group will have to solve one problem using Arduino and other resources of the STEAM-Lab. The problems will be given by the professor and each group can choose one of them or propose another one (in this case, the teacher must approve the new project):
 1. Feel music without hearing
 2. Improve the common blind cane
 3. Design a good virtual assistant for old people

4. Design a good educational robot for kids

After all the sessions, the students must deliver a worksheet memory about the project (includes the main ideas, objectives, work plan, designs, photos, Arduino codes, ideas of improvement, etc.)

5. Results/Evidence

- The completion of the three practices.
- The implication of the project.
- The worksheet memory was delivered at the end of the project.
- The final result/product.

Observations/Personal Notes

This unit plan can be adapted to other topics changing the problems given by the teacher. It's very moldable

13.- Intelligent house (La Salle Congrs)

Age Average:	16-17	Teaching Hours:	10
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL	CL DTM	IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

Construction of an intelligent house

2. Materials/Resources

- Arduino kit (Arduino, sensors, wires, protoboard...).
- Access to 3D and 2D design software: Tinkercad, Cura, GIMP, Canva, etc.
- Access to 3D printer, vinyl cutter, CNC, and laser engraving.
- Access to cardboard, wood, methacrylate, paints, projector, blackboard, workbench, tools, and others.
- Access to protocols and guidelines.

3. Learning Objectives

- Arduino constructions and code.
- Build up a scaled object (a house in this case).
- Integrate the 3D printing, vinyl cutter, hand tools, and other resources with the Arduino system.
- Inclusive thinking.

4. Unit Plan Outline

The plan will take around 12 sessions:

- The starting session will be a discussion with the students about how to create an intelligent, sustainable house and what elements we must consider along the project (position, controlling, etc.). Like a brainstorming session.
- We will also consider the social viewpoint of this house. Human rights are collected and everybody has the right to have adequate housing. So, should homeless people have access to this type of house?
- After that, for the next 10 lessons, the teacher will divide the students into groups of 5-6 students each. They will work in a group.
- In the end, we will show the different products and discuss the process of tinkering with each house.
- After that, each group must deliver a worksheet on memory completed about the project (consists of the work plan, the ideas, problems that they had during the project, Arduino code, design of the house, things to improve, etc.).

5. Results/Evidence

- Participation in the first brainstorming session and discussion.
- The worksheet memory was delivered at the end of the project. This item is the most important one.
- The final product.

Observations/Personal Notes

14.- The cell (SSIG Vincenza Poloni)

Age Average:	11-12	Teaching Hours:	6
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL	DTM	IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

Define cells, and look at how cells interact with their environments through cellular transport. Next, students look at the differences between prokaryotic and eukaryotic cells and then study the structures and functions of the organelles in these cells. The unit ends with a comparison of plant and animal cells and a look at how unicellular organisms carry out all life functions with just one cell.

2. Materials/Resources

- Lab materials (microscopes, dry mount slides, etc.).
- iPad
- Quiver Education App.
- Recycle materials.

3. Learning Objectives

- Develop scientific inquiry skills, by making sense of an experience or answer a question using evidence and scientific understanding.
- Develop practical skills that include good observation, measurement, and equipment handling skills so that learners can collect accurate and reliable data.
- Using a compound microscope.
- Preparing a dry mount slide.
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities and promoting a cooperation positively.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Learn about animal cell, and plant cell function through a variety of approaches (active learning):
 - Research,
 - Discussion,
 - Listening,
 - Reading, ...
- Use QuiverApp (Augmented reality) as a review.
- Observation at the microscope.
- Realize a digital experience laboratory book
- Realize a 3D model of plant and animal cells with recycled materials.

5. Results/Evidence

Digital experience lab book (Including photo, video...), and the 3D cells model.

Observations/Personal Notes

15.- Circuit of resistors and capacitors (Scuola Maria Ausiliatrice)

Age Average:	17-18	Teaching Hours:	4
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	Physics
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL	CL DTM	IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

Let's show how to make a circuit of resistors and capacities in our physical laboratory

2. Materials/Resources

- Video.
- LEDs.
- Schemes
- Graphs.
- Analysis method.
- Statistical methods.

3. Learning Objectives

- Flexibility.
- Production.
- Improve creativity.

4. Unit Plan Outline

Scheduling physical laboratories once or twice a month to improve a positive approach to this subject

5. Results/Evidence

Improving productivity and creativity to make a physical object and sharing the learning improvements when students study a particular physics chapter.

Observations/Personal Notes

16.- Steam in the school (S.Umiltà_ Faenza)

Age Average:	11-14	Teaching Hours:	5 hours for primary school, 7 h for 1st year of middle school, 12 h the second, and 15 h the third course.								
Subjects	S	T	E	A	M	Others:					
Curricular	II	EC	DG	Diversity GAP		G	I	E	R	D	Others:
Instruction	AL	PBL		PLIE	SL	CL	DTM	IBL	T	Other:	

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

The idea is to increase the tinkering, co-working, problem-solving capacities. Helping the students to overcome their disabilities (and the ones of their classmates) and to develop a successful project.

2. Materials/Resources

- 3D printer.
- Cardboard.
- Laser cutter.
- Math and science models

3. Learning Objectives

- To make children passionate about school.
- Build affection for scientific disciplines.
- Connect the school to concrete projects.
- Create a bridge between steam subjects (overall vision and not individual disciplines).

4. Unit Plan Outline

- For 5th primary school:
 - Rocket model (with QR-code description) (science, technology).
- 1 year of middle school:
 - Cardboard castles (art, technology, history).
 - Micro:bit labs.
- 2-year middle school:
 - Building cities models second year (art, civics, technology).
 - Stained glass windows with vinyl cutter (technology, art).
 - Cardboard and 3d printing of solids for boardgame pawns (technology, Italian detective stories storytelling)
- 3rd-year middle school
 - Building renewable energy models third year (science, technology, civics)
 - CINEMA LAB: photography, film sounds recording (art, technology, music)
 - 3D printing of a room (technology, art)

5. Results/Evidence

They will be evaluated by the quality of their work, the participation of each group member, and the collaboration among them.

Observations/Personal Notes

17.- 3D Charts (S.Umiltà_ Faenza)

Age Average:	11-12	Teaching Hours:	10
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG Diversity GAP G I E R D	Others:	
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL DTM IBL T	Other:	

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn about Charts with the help of new technologies and 3D models. We'll learn about the different types of charts, how to collect data in science, and how to build a chart with a 3D printer using Tinkercad.

2. Materials/Resources

- Graph paper.
- Rain gauge.
- Cardboards.
- 3D printer.
- Tinkercad.

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about the mathematical chart charts: pie, bar, column, line, area, and cartesian plane.
- Learn the use of Tinkercad.
- Develop a scientific method of data collection. Collecting data from rain gauge every week and transforming it into visive data.
- Cooperate positively.
- Increase student's problem-solving capacities

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: Frontal lesson about the experimental method - measurements - measurement errors.
- Session 2: Discussion with students about the scientific method of collecting data.
- Session 3-4-5: Tables and graphs in science (rain and temperatures) and math.
- Session 6-7-8-9: During technology, each group will prepare a 3D chart model of the assigned data using colors, cardboard, 3D printed components, and graph paper with their data, chart, and a brief presentation.
- Session 10: they will present their work to the class.

5. Results/Evidence

- 3D model chart.
- A graph paper with their data, chart, and a brief presentation.

Observations/Personal Notes

It will be difficult for them to collaborate on the same graph, but it will be good if each one manages to do a different part of the assignment. We prefer not to use Excel or Sheets because we want to teach it better in the third year.

18.- Repair air chamber (S.Umiltà_ Faenza)

Age Average:	11-12	Teaching Hours:	3
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL DTM	IBL	T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn about air, water, plastic properties, pressure, and how to repair a broken bicycle air chamber.

2. Materials/Resources

- Plastic air chamber.
- Basins.
- Water.
- colored marker.
- plastic patch.

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn that air doesn't mix with water.
- Learn what is pressure and how pressure moves air.
- Learn how to detect a hole in the air chamber and how to repair it.
- Make students more autonomous (particularly girls and disabled ones).

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: Science lesson about air and water.
- Session 2: Science lesson about pressure.
- Session 3: Technology practical lesson about how to repair a wheel.

5. Results/Evidence

- The practical activity of repairing.
- Oral evaluation of the relative knowledge

Observations/Personal Notes

Maybe it can be implemented with a questionnaire

19.- Yeast and temperature (S.Umiltà_ Faenza)

Age Average:	12-13	Teaching Hours:	4
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL	DTM	IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn how temperature is important for microorganisms' growth and food conservation.

2. Materials/Resources

- Flour.
- Brewer's yeast.
- Water.
- Micro-bit.
- Computer (with google sheets and micro-bit website).

3. Learning Objectives

- Develop abilities in micro-bit programming.
- Increase the knowledge of microorganisms' natural phenomena.
- Add some practical examples of food technology.
- Discuss bacterial growth curve as a possible exponential curve.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: Technology Lesson about food technology cooling conservation and leavening of bread.
- Session 2: Science lesson about microorganisms and yeasts. Each student will have to look for the ideal conditions of life for a different bacterium.
- Session 3: Informatic lesson about micro-bit programming to detect temperature.
- Session 4: Technology experiment of bread's leavening at different temperatures (with micro-bit temperature control).
- Session 5: Math and science. Discussion between the exponential curve and the curve of bacteria in natural condition

5. Results/Evidence

They will write a short review of this experiment.

Observations/Personal Notes

Maybe it can be implemented with a questionnaire.

20.- Renewable energy model (S.Umiltà_ Faenza)

Age Average:	13-14	Teaching Hours:	7
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE	SL CL DTM	IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn about renewable energy production with the help of 3D models and slide presentations. We'll learn about the theory behind energy transmission and how renewable energy works.

2. Materials/Resources

- Computer.
- 3D printer.
- Recycled materials.
- Vinyl cutter.

3. Learning Objectives

- Increase students problem solving abilities.
- Cooperate positively.
- Increase their presenting abilities.
- Learn how renewable sources work by observing the models.
- Develop practical skills that include good observation, measurement, and equipment handling skills so that learners can collect accurate and reliable data.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1-2: Introduction to renewable energies.
- Session 3-4: Group research and Google slide presentation.
- Session 5-6-7: Cooperative model building each group has a different renewable energy source, they have to prepare a project, a list of the materials, and a final presentation

5. Results/Evidence

3D models, with PowerPoint presentations and a final Google, form personal quiz, and a SWAT group analysis

Observations/Personal Notes

21.- The waves (S.Umiltà_ Faenza)

Age Average:	13-14	Teaching Hours:	8
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	Music
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL	DTM IBL T	Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn about the waves with the help of new technologies and 3D models. We'll learn about earthquake, sound, and radio waves and they will represent in each group an experiment about them.

2. Materials/Resources

- Music box.
- Basic kit: Sand, candle, bowl, and recycled material.
- Scotch tape.

3. Learning Objectives

- To learn more about the waves and their behavior.
- To learn how to do experiments.
- To learn how to cooperate in experimental group work.
- To learn to link different subjects.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: Science introductions about earthquake waves.
- Session 2: Music introduction about music waves.
- Session 3: Science lesson about wave behavior.
- Session 4: Technology lesson about the application of waves in telecommunications.
- Session 5: Teachers experiment with waves.
- Session 6: Students group work to prepare their experiment about waves.
- Session 7: Presentation of their experiments to the class.
- Session 8: Test the waves and the experiments.

5. Results/Evidence

- Video of the experiment.
- Final test.

Observations/Personal Notes

22.- The Age of discovery (S.Umiltà_ Faenza)

Age Average:	12-13	Teaching Hours:	7
Subjects	S T E A M	Others: Geography // History	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL	CL DTM	IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

The students will learn history and geography by playing a board game they prepared by themselves. They will also learn to collaborate.

2. Materials/Resources

- Cardboard.
- A3 sheets and colors.
- 3D printer.
- Computer.

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn how to use doodle3d to print 3d objects.
- Learn how is the world map.
- Learn to respect the proportion in a map.
- Learn more about the historical period of the age of discoveries.
- Learn to collaborate.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: Study the historical period of the age of discoveries.
- Session 2: Preparation of the cards with the question of the age of discoveries.
- Session 3-4: The students, in groups, prepare the board game map with the map of the world and divide it into cells.
- Session 5-6: Each student will print a pawn with a ship shape using doodle 3D.
- Session 7: Students will play with the boardgame and they have to reach India answering historical questions

5. Results/Evidence

The board games and the history tests.

Observations/Personal Notes

23.- The castle (S.Umiltà_ Faenza)

Age Average:	11-12	Teaching Hours:	5
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	History
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL	CL DTM	IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

The students will study castles in history so, we asked them to improve their tinkering ability by building a 3D model of a castle in a 4-student group.

2. Materials/Resources

Recycled material

3. Learning Objectives

The students will learn how to manage the timeline, divide the assignments, to be creative and collaborative. They must also link their practical work to the historical lesson

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: Lesson about history.
- Session 2: Write down a personal idea, divide it into groups, and build a common project.
- Session 3: Start the main structure construction.
- Session 4: Define details.
- Session 5: Show the final Castle, and make a questionnaire about their collaborative skills and their feedback.

5. Results/Evidence

Questionnaires and the 3D castle.

Observations/Personal Notes

24.- STOP water pollution (San Giuseppe Valbrembo, Bergamo / San Giovanni Bosco)

Age Average:	13-14	Teaching Hours:	6
Subjects	S T E A M	Others: Geography // Languages	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL DTM	IBL T	Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn to use Scratch by creating a spot to raise awareness about water pollution in different states on all continents. They will project a dialogue or a narration that must be graphically appealing and engaging for the stakeholders.

2. Materials/Resources

- Visual programming: Scratch.
- Interactive maps: Google Maps, Google Earth.
- Video/image/sound editing (Photoshop, Canva, Moviemaker, Audacity...).
- Lab materials: PC, iPad, or Android Tablet.
- Individually collected information.
- Digital book.

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- <https://www.nationalgeographic.it/>
- <https://www.focus.it/>
- <https://www.istockphoto.com/it>
- <https://youtu.be/Bq37CeP37-8>

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about water pollution: causes, impacts, and possible solutions.
- Identify different kinds of pollution and environmental and health damages.
- Develop scientific inquiry skills, by making sense of an experience or answer a question using evidence and scientific understanding.
- Develop practical skills that include grammatical structure, and morphosyntax with a focus on relevance and appropriateness in dialogues and narration.
- Use Scratch.
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Practice cooperating positively.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1 (1h 30 min): We'll start with brainstorming and writing what is water pollution for us. The Mentimeter link is <https://www.menti.com/>. We'll start our discussion to share our opinions and points of view. Then the teachers will explain the activity and the visual program Scratch. We'll see a tutorial: <https://youtu.be/Bq37CeP37-8>. Will be created five groups of four students each, paying attention to all the student's diversity. The roles in each group will be a screenwriter, a graphic designer, and two executive assistants (dialogues and movements).
- Session 2 (1h): Next, students will plan their project before creating it with Scratch.
- Session 3 (2h 30 min): The students will create and finalize their project.
- Session 4 (1h): Share and explain their work. Evaluation.

5. Results/Evidence

- Individually collected information.
- e-portfolio: digital experience lab book (including photo, video...)
- The final product.

Observations/Personal Notes

The teachers recommend paying attention to all kinds of needs of the companions and social issues of modern society. It's important to give them enough time to explore and to create with autonomy.

25.- The universal Language (Collegio Bianconi – Scuola Cappelletti Turco)

Age Average:	11-12	Teaching Hours:	6
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL DTM IBL T	Other:	
		Others: Combine different cognitive styles // Improve autonomy	

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn about geometrical transformations and the use of the same language in art and music.

2. Materials/Resources

- iPad or Android Tablet.
- Visual programming: Scratch.
- Recycled materials.

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

For Session 1:

- Starting video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PfoZq9WieZA>
- Images:

For Session 2 (Exercise about geometrical translation in Scratch):

- Starting video: <https://scratch.mit.edu/projects/650415673>

- Example for Challenge 1: <https://youtu.be/x6UZW5U0XeE>
- Example for Challenge 2: <https://youtu.be/Za0eJwV8jvk>
- Example for Challenge 3: <https://scratch.mit.edu/projects/598337951>

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about geometrical transformations: translations, symmetries, and similarity.
- Connect mathematical language with art and music using the same structure.
- Develop practical skills that include good observation, and measurement.
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Practice positively cooperating in pairs.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1 (1 hour): We'll start with a video making us questions about which kind of transformations they can recognize (active investigation, discussion, listening, ...).
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PfoZq9WieZA>
 - Brainstorming: they will start making a list of observed transformations and watching again the video they will also identify the ones lost. Teacher will explain how mathematical language is represented in repetitive artistic elements and musical phrases (images)

Modules in art

- Session 2 (2 hours): They will practice an exercise prepared using scratch about geometrical translation:
 - <https://scratch.mit.edu/projects/650415673>
 - They will start a new Scratch project:
 - Challenge 1: create shapes in the plan (use the extension "Pen"; see an example <https://youtu.be/x6UZW5U0XeE>)
 - Challenge 2: create a new sprite and import it in Scratch. This sprite is the artistic element (to remove the background <https://youtu.be/Za0eJwV8jvk>).
 - Challenge 3: Connect the same geometrical shapes with the artistic element (see an example <https://scratch.mit.edu/projects/598337951>)
 - Challenge 4: Choose a sound in Scratch that matches the artistic element.
 - Challenge 5: Connect the sound to the artistic element.

- Session 3 (1 hour): Challenge 6. Geometric similarity: focus on changing the size of shapes in the plan, changing the color of the corresponding artistic element, and modifying bpm in music.
- Session 4 (1 hour): Final Test: Each pair will receive a different phrase with repetitions (A A) or variations (A A₁) and will start a new Scratch project to translate it through the practiced languages.
- Session 5 (1 hour): Share the project with the other pairs.

5. Results/Evidence

- Scratch project
- Final test

Observations/Personal Notes

It's important to give them enough time to explore and to create with autonomy. Additional improvement: students can increase their knowledge of this universal language by building some artistic friezes with recycled materials and/or by inventing a piece of music with repetitions.

26.- HYPERGLIDER (Istituto Sacro Cuore e Fondazione Marri-S. Umiltà)

Age Average:	13-14	Teaching Hours:	8
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	Physics
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL	CL DTM IBL T	Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

The didactic unit wants to use play and the positive competition to lead children to think about their potential and about the waste material that our society produces, and to work with their own hands. Main competences to develop cooperative learning, and abstraction thinking.

2. Materials/Resources

- 3 Micro:bit.
- 2 Alimentation support.
- Material to be recycled
- Computer.
- Didactic videos.

2 b) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- Model airplane race
- Glider race
- Paper plane race
- Games built by waste

3. Learning Objectives

Recognize the potential of recycled material and think of alternative solutions using only this, learn to build with your hands: structures, covers, aerodynamics, and solidity. knowing how to recognize their talents and enhance them to divide roles within the group

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Statement of the goal: a glider race. Introductory lesson (video-learning) group discussion on the theme of recycling and ecology. (KAHOOT game).
- How do airplanes work (brainstorming on possible materials to use), basic concepts of aerodynamics: WHAT IS IMPORTANT FOR A GLIDER? Begin to privately collect suitable recycling material.
- Introduction programming with Micro:bit (PRACTICE LEARNING), a small group exercise on how to build a simple program. The division into groups and identification of the coding group.

- Study of the characteristics of the material to maximize lift (time in flight) and reduce impact. think about weight and size (gliders online search) and also the coding group.
- Beginning glider design (cooperative learning) through proportional schemes provided by the teacher, the first approach to the materials, and finally, brainstorming for the design before building. The coding group becomes familiar with Micro:bit, and exercises. mid-way feedback.
- First constructions and prototype tests, coding group test.
- Refinement and improvement for functional projects.
- Race with glider evaluation and coding (glory award) finally focus group and feedback.

5. Results/Evidence

Feedback and final questionnaire and realization of the models

Observations/Personal Notes

It's important to give them enough time to explore and to create with autonomy. The project must be perceived and presented as a game, learning also derives from fun and the spirit of positive competition.

27.- GeomeTRY (Fond. Marri-S.Umiltà Faenza, scuola Cappelletti-Turco Colognola ai Colli, Istituto S.Sisto)

Age Average:	11-12	Teaching Hours:	6
Subjects	S T E A M	Others: Languages; (Artistic implementation)	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL	CL DTM	IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit plan, the students will learn about solid geometry with the help of new technologies and 3D models. We will learn about vertexes, faces, and edges in 3 or more languages.

2. Materials/Resources

- Micro:bit.
- Computer.
- Aluminum sheets.
- Cardboard.
- Cables.
- Glue.
- Permanent markers.
- Wooden sticks.
- Cutter.
- Pencil.
- Set square.

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about the different elements of a solid figure in different languages: vertexes, edges, and faces.
- Develop practical skills that include good observation, measurement, and equipment handling skills.
- Use of Micro:bit program.

- Practice cooperating positively.
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Empowerment of orthogonal projection.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: An introductory lesson about the different solid components. Each student is asked to bring a cubic object from home. We will teach different parts of the solid figure. In the specific case: the cube (vertexes, edges, faces).
- Session 2-3: The students have previous knowledge about Micro:bit. Students get instruction on what to do and they have to try to make it work.
- Session 4-5: The students have previous knowledge about plane figures construction. Working in pairs, students will design the development of a solid figure through the use of set squares on recycling material (cardboard sheet). They will continue their work constructing the solid object, cutting cardboard, and pasting part of it. Before pasting, they should locate wires and the aluminum sheet in the specific parts of the cube.
- Session 5-6: The test. We will ask them the name of the different components.

5. Results/Evidence

- The oral test at the end and the 3D model. We verify their knowledge and if the model works.
- Observations/Personal Notes.
- Optional comments or recommendations.
 - We can implement the activity with more names of the components (lateral/ bottom face/edge; opposite vertex etc.).
 - We can also add an artistic part with the decoration of the faces and colors (and we can add symmetry, complementary colors, color theory...etc etc...).

Observations/Personal Notes

<https://makecode.microbit.org/RaPXVHhUPdm9>

28.- Let's solve the case! (Manfredini)

Age Average:	12-13	Teaching Hours:	11
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	Literature
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL	CL DTM	IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will project and build a maze based on a thriller story, read before during literature lessons. They will project the maze by drawing a technical design respecting proportions. The maze also has to be built following the setting of the story. They will program a Lego Mindstorms robot by EV3 to let it go out of the maze. The robot will find clues during the path and at the exit, it will discover the solution to the case.

2. Materials/Resources

- Artistic elements: paper, paint, brush, glue, etc .
- iPad.
- Lego Mindstorms.
- Technical design tools.
- Recycled materials.

2 1) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

Thriller sheet, Vademecum Lego Mindstorms

3. Learning Objectives

- Use the specific elements of the thriller genre.
- Apply proportionality in technical design.
- Develop project skills.
- Develop creativity.
- Develop manual skills.
- Develop computational thinking.
- Discover personal attitudes by exploring a different kinds of activities.
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Practice cooperating positively.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1 (1h): Teachers present the project to the classes, divide the students into groups (3/4 person) and give each group a different thriller story.

- Session 2 (half an hour): Students fill out a sheet shared on Google Classroom from literature teachers where they focus on the specific elements of the story.
- Session 3 (half an hour): Students choose the clues (from 3 to 6) that they will insert into the maze.
- Session 4 (1h): Students project the maze. They draw the path on paper using technical design tools: the teachers give them a preformed paper and tell them the proportion to use.
- Session 5 (2h): The students using Lego Mindstorms have to program the robot to go out of the maze by adding color and ultrasonic sensors. When the robot faces a clue it will declare it.
- Session 6 (2h): The students build the maze following their project, they use recycled materials. In the maze, they insert decorative elements linked to the setting of the story.
- Session 7 (2h): The students test their robot in the maze and if it doesn't work they try to find a solution.
- Session 8 (2h): Each group share with the class their project.

5. Results/Evidence

- The Maze model with recycled materials (photos, videos).
- EV3 program.
- Oral exposition of the project.

Observations/Personal Notes

29.- TimeOut (G.M., Roma and I.C. Polo2, Gelatina)

Age Average:	13-14	Teaching Hours:	6
Subjects	S T E A M	Others: Mother Language // Music	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity	GAP G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL	CL DTM	IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan students will make an audiovisual timer including a countdown combined with an alternation of chromatic and musical notes. This timer will be used in eventual other educational activities.

2. Materials/Resources

- Laptop, iPad or Android Tablet.
- Kit Micro:bit (software + electronic parts).

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

Tutorial link: <https://youtu.be/MMqKMGeykM8> First steps with Micro:bit.

2 b) Materials/Resources - Documents (optional)

- <http://www.omstad.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/Microbit.pdf> User manual
- <https://www.cieliparalleli.com/scienza-e-tecnologia/i-colori-delliride-e-i-chakra.html>

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about: chromatic and musical notes and how to combine them, elements of computer programming.
- Develop practical skills that include good observation, measurement, and assembling electrical components.
- Use Micro:bit programming software.
- Record the activity's steps.
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Practice cooperating positively.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1 (1h): Element of programming and first approach to Micro:bit using materials in the attachment; students are divided into groups of 4.
- Session 2 (1,5h): Students will program and assemble the timer complete with the countdown (recording the activity).
- Session 3 (1,5 h): Students will compose and add the melody to their timer (recording the activity).
- Session 4 (1,5): Students will match colored led lights to each note, programming and connecting them to the timer (recording the activity).
- Session 5 (1 h): Each group will present its work. Evaluation.

5. Results/Evidence

- Physical and simulated timers.
- Digital experience lab book (including photo, video...).

Observations/Personal Notes

The evaluation will consider the following:

- Positive interaction among the students of the same group.
- Deadlines
- Validity of the chromatic and musical combination
- The functionality of the timer.
- Link: <https://makecode.microbit.org/#editorù>

30.- Knowing Micro:bit, basic tools (Scuola Media Maria Ausiliatrice, Rome)

Age Average:	10-11	Teaching Hours:	6
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE	SL CL DTM	IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn about the basic information and functions of Micro:bit hardware through standard lectures and practical exercises designed to be carried out individually or in groups.

2. Materials/Resources

- Teachers and Students.
- Internet connection.
- Android Tablet or PC.
- Micro:bit hardware

2 b) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

Link to Micro:bit programming website <https://makecode.microbit.org/>

3. Learning Objectives

- Gain knowledge and awareness of informatic tools.
- Learn and apply base coding when and where required
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Practice cooperating positively.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: Micro:bit Introduction (1 hour). We'll start with an introduction to the meaning of coding with blocks. We will then guide the students with a practical exercise about making a predefined logo appear at the start of the micro:bit hardware, then let the students make their own (can be done in pairs).
- Session 2: Input and output: Micro:bit senses (1 hour). We'll teach the main sensors of Micro:bit to guide the students with practical exercises around pressing buttons and reading outputs from the display (such as numbers and words), then let the students try to make the words or numbers they want appear.
- Session 3: Shake and dance: Micro:bit accelerometer and play function (1 hour). We'll teach the main sensors of Micro:bit to guide the students with practical exercises around gently shaking the hardware and listening to the outputs played (such as predefined melodies), then let the students try to make their melodies played by the hardware.

- Session 4: Random number of joy: Micro:bit simple variables (1 hour). We'll introduce the concept of a random number generated from a restricted range and fix its value. We will then guide the students in Micro:bit with practical exercises to let them observe different outputs on the display (such as happy or sad faces) depending on the value obtained ("If-else function"), then let the students try to create two melodies to be played in case of a good or bad outcome.
- Session 5: Evaluation Test (1 hour). The students are required to do a test based on all the previous lessons.
- Session 6: Test Check and Feedback (1 hour). Evaluate student's progress, and see what has been done correctly and what needs to be improved.

5. Results/Evidence

- The evaluation test is a good tool to verify students' skills using coding.
- Watching over the students working in pairs.

Observations/Personal Notes

For following units, students could be asked to do exercises before receiving guidance from the teacher, to see how they will approach Micro:bit on their own.

31.- SalleBOT (La Salle Palamós, Girona-Catalunya)

Age Average:	6-7		Teaching Hours:	6-10						
Subjects	S	T	E	A	M	Others: Emotional Education				
Curricular	II	EC	DG	Diversity GAP	G	I	E	R	D	Others:
Instruction	AL	PBL	PLIE	SL	CL	DTM	IBL	T	Other:	

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

The main idea of this unit plan is to introduce code and robotics at the beginning of primary education. That's important to understand the first lessons in Computational with a robot surface. Firstly, students will be able to compare the different robot parts comparing with their bodies, they will use a robot whose movements are assimilable to those of children. Finally, they will program a surface robot on small boards. The topics for the boards are varied, at the beginning they are only used to train code lessons, then content located in the official curriculum will be worked on.

2. Materials/Resources

- Recycling materials.
- Surface robot boards.
- Surface robots.
- Covers/costumes for robots.

3. Learning Objectives

- Identify and relate the different parts of a robot and its functions to the body itself.
- Develop movement codes on the surface.
- Exploring multiple programming alternatives by making estimates: the longest route, the shortest route, and similar routes.
- Using robotics to work on emotional education.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Lesson 1: Micro:bit Introduction (1 hour). We'll start with an introduction to the meaning of coding with blocks. We will then guide the students with a practical exercise about making a predefined logo appear at the start of the micro:bit hardware, then let the students make their own (can be done in pairs).
- Session 1: WE ARE ROBOTS. To start, we will make the robot vest, so we will use a vest made of a garbage bag or some recycled fabric. We will decorate it with the keypad and show the students the space we will use to do robotics. We will group the students in pairs and play programming, imitating the movements of the robots.
- Session 2: WE DISCOVER THE BIG SALLEBOT. In this session, we will train exercises to practice code with the big robot and with experienced movements. The exercises are simple and cover a few blocks. Programming challenges focus on thinking about the different pathways that can lead to a successful program.

- Session 3: LET'S PROGRAMMING. This activity is aimed at improving the knowledge of the code through more complex exercises, where the itineraries are already given but contain more instructions than in the previous session.
- Session 4: WE DISCOVER THE SMALL SALLEBOT. In this session, we will introduce the small "sallebot" and review the contents worked on so far, on the one hand, the robot parts, and the code blocks, on the other the new boards with the introduction of challenges related to school content.
- Session 5 PROGRAMMING AND REPROGRAMMING. For this session, we will train multiple code programs for the surface robot with complex instructions.
 - spaces where it is not forbidden to pass.
 - just steps back.
 - short itinerary and long itinerary.
 - combination of two robots together without colliding.
 - combination of two robots with reverse displacements.
 - 1 can only go forward and the other can only go back.
- Session 6: EMOTIONAL ROBOT. In this session, there will be work on basic emotions. Work on a story about emotions and practical cases of identification and emotional management
- Session 7: ASSESSMENT. A couple of children have to show their programming skills with a small "sallebot" on the surface doing an itinerary with more than 6 blocks of code, forward and backward. The teacher will fill in a rubric according to the skills shown by the student.

5. Results/Evidence

To be able to program a surface robot forward and backward with more than 6 code blocks.

Observations/Personal Notes

32.- Helping our planet (I.C. Polo 2)

Age Average:	10-11	Teaching Hours:	5-6
Subjects	S T E A M	Others: Foreign languages	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL	PLIE SL CL	DTM IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan students from the final class of Primary School and from the first class of Secondary School will learn together the meaning of Agenda 2030 and the content of one goal with the help of new technologies and 3D. They'll learn the twelfth sustainable development goal through practical activities and games.

2. Materials/Resources

- Lab materials: ESCORNABOT
- Recycled material.
- Drawing or writing materials.

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

https://youtu.be/wWR_voTs6j0

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about Agenda 2030 and Goal 12: Responsible Consumption and Production
- Take care of oceans
- Save the resources of our planet and learn to reuse and transform products sustainably.
- Develop practical skills that include good observation and measurement
- Develop computational thinking
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Practice cooperating positively.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: We'll start with a brainstorming activity to understand what students know about oceans. Teachers could ask them: What do you think there is in the depth of oceans?

- Session 2: Students will watch a video about “The plastic continent”: https://youtu.be/wWR_voTs6j0 then the teacher could ask them their opinion about it and guide the discussion towards Agenda 2030.
- Session 3: Next, students will talk in pairs: they look at the differences between various materials of some objects through the observation of pictures and they talk together about the situations in which we use something made of plastic; they will observe if plastic materials could be reused in a different way like paper for example.
- Session 4: The teacher will guide students in a discussion (Circle time) to teach them that many plastic products can be transformed into a new objects.
- Session 5: Turtle game.
 - The teacher makes a square field, which reflects the ocean.
 - The scouts and guides are divided into turtles and plastic pieces floating around in the ocean.
 - Those who are turtles must crawl around. Those who are plastic pieces must do the crab walk.
 - The turtles should now try to move from one end of the ocean to the other without being touched/ caught by a plastic piece.
 - If a turtle is touched by a piece of plastic, it turns into plastic.
 - The last turtle still alive to swim through the ocean without getting touched by plastic wins the game!
- Session 6: Students in pairs will project and create a square field on paper that represents the ocean, and they will draw some waste objects. They write the shortest path to pick up rubbish by using coding language.
- Session 7: Students verify their code by using escornabot. In case of a mistake, they must rewrite their code.

- Session 8: Share it with a short presentation to the mates. Evaluation.

5. Results/Evidence

E-portfolio: digital experience lab book (including photo, video...)

Observations/Personal Notes

Students like this activity a lot. It’s important to give them enough time to explore and to create with autonomy. The students train in cooperation and a sense of responsibility.

33.- Space 2.0 (Fondazione Marri Sant'Umiltà – Faenza)

Age Average:	6-8	Teaching Hours:	5-6
Subjects	S T E A M	Others: Geography, physical education, English	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL	CL DTM	IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this unit plan the students can learn to move in the space of their school first with their body, then on paper, and in addition, programming the movement with Lego spike or with Bee bot for the younger ones.

2. Materials/Resources

- Tape to do a grid on the ground.
- Lab materials: paper, pencil, crayons.
- iPad or Android Tablet.
- Recycled materials.

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about the orientation and direction: go up, go down, left, right.
- Develop geographic skills making the plant of the class or the school.
- Develop practical skills that include good observation, measurement, and equipment handling skills so that learners can collect accurate and reliable data.
- Use common tools.
- Build the robot using the instructions
- Program the movement of the robot
- Increase students' problem-solving and social abilities

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: We'll start with an observation of the class/school with a variety of approaches (active investigation, discussion, photos, pictures, listening.). They will start painting the plant with the teacher.
- Session 2: Next, students will be divided into groups to reproduce it adding some details.
- Session 3: in the gym, the students can move following commands of the teacher in L2.
- Session 4: then, the students do the same on paper using a pawn.
- Session: 5- 6: In groups, the students create a robot with Lego Wedo (Lunar rover) and they program it to move in space on paper.
- Session 7: Share it with a short presentation to the mates. Evaluation.

5. Results/Evidence

Improve observation and competence in coding and digital skills.

Observations/Personal Notes

Students like this activity a lot. It's important to give them enough time to explore and to create with autonomy.

34.- Disposing waste is also fun! (Benedetta Cambiagio, Rome)

Age Average:	9-10	Teaching Hours:	6
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	Civics, English
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL	DTM IBL T	Other: Flipped Classroom

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn the importance of proper waste disposal while having fun creating a prototype. They will find that recycling is fun and important for the future of the environment.

2. Materials/Resources

- Lim.
- Ipad/Tablet.
- Lego Spike.
- Stationery material.
- Internet.
- Worksheets.

2. a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- https://youtu.be/mDpK_MNOg94
- <https://youtu.be/A4eWAMB3Z0Q>

Worksheets:

Recycling Sorting

Colour in and cut out the images and stick them in the correct box in the table.

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn the importance of waste separation.
- Make aware of how each gesture can produce a change in daily life.
- Decode the instructions considering a final product to be made.
- Knowing how to make an artifact distinguishing between shapes, numbers, and colors.
- Participate effectively in the cooperative group.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: We will start showing a video on recycling, after which we will propose a brainstorming on the ecological footprint of each. Then we will show a second video on the consequences of incorrect disposal. The video is about the so-called "Plastic Islands". They will discuss how to prevent this in the future.
- Session 2: Pupils are divided into groups and each group is associated with a disposal material with its color: blue is paper, yellow is plastic, green is glass and red is organic waste. Each group is asked to imagine a hypothetical "waste-eating monster" and to draw it.
- Session 3: As a homework assignment, they will have to research their reference refusal.
- Session 4: Another day the pupils, divided into their groups, receive the Lego Spike material with the associated devices. They must create the "waste-eating monster" by following the instructions on the App, making it react to the presence of the garbage of the relative color.
- Session 5: Classmates show each other the work done, explaining the history of that material and the time it takes to decompose if left in the environment.
- Session 6: At the end, an exhibition will be created in which each group will present to the whole school both the artifact and the poster with the history of their material/waste.
- Session 7: Evaluation. The teacher will observe the final product of each group and will evaluate it with a special observation/evaluation grid. Students will evaluate themselves with a self-completed Likert-scale questionnaire. In addition, there will be feedback among peers in which they will discuss their teamwork experiences in the group.

5. Results/Evidence

The students enjoyed studying in this inspiring way. Working in a group is always inclusive and profitable for all types of intelligence and different learning styles.

35.- Kandinsky made by a Robot (Manfredini, Varese)

Age Average:	10-11	Teaching Hours:	6
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL	DTM IBL T	Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, the students will experiment with geometric design through the use of a robot created with Lego Spike essential.

2 a) Materials/Resources

- Lego Spike essential and app.
- iPad.
- Markers.
- Paper.

2 b) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- Lego Spike App.
- Unit Taxi, Taxi!

3. Learning Objectives

- Introduce the students to abstract art.
- Basic programming with Lego Spike.
- How to create an artistic work.
- Learning by playing.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: Video presentation of Kandinsky and his works (operas)
- Session 2: Analysis of the works, recognizing the geometric figures present, analyzing their characteristics, and reproducing them on a sheet.
- Session 3:
 - Presentation of the robot and construction in small groups.
 - Realization through trial and error of lines, straight lines, squares, triangles, rectangles, and circles.
 - Improvement of the drawing by coloring the figures using different techniques (pencils and watercolors).

5. Results/Evidence

- Photos and videos of the realization of the shapes through the robot.
- Exhibition of the completed works.

Observations/Personal Notes

36.- Clear our city with Verdino (Santa Sofia di Civitavecchia)

Age Average:	6-8		Teaching Hours:	16						
Subjects	S	T	E	A	M	Others: Geography				
Curricular	II	EC	DG	Diversity GAP	G	I	E	R	D	Others:
Instruction	AL	PBL	PLIE	SL	CL	DTM	IBL	T	Other:	

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn about separate waste sorting.

2. Materials/Resources

- iPad or Android Tablet.
- Lego Spike.
- Recycled materials.
- Paper.
- Arrow keys.
- Art box/pencil case.

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

<https://education.lego.com/es-es/downloads/spike-app/software>

3. Learning Objectives

- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Practice cooperating positively.
- Learn spatial indicators.
- Identify and design the recognized materials through the five senses.
- Know the objectives of the 2030 agenda.
- First approach to computational thinking.
- Know and use Lego Spike.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: Raise children's awareness of the subject (group discussion, debate, stimulus questions, observation of the environment).
- Session 2: Games with lattices and paths with the body.
- Session 3: Games with lattices and paths with arrows.
- Session 4: Observe to recognize the materials.
- Session 5: Representing the path on the grid by positioning the various materials.
- Session 6: Building Verdino with Lego Spike.
- Session 7: Create the sequence of instructions for Verdino with the arrows.
- Session 8: Construction of the path on the ground, of a lattice using different materials.
- Session 9: Challenge.

5. Results/Evidence

E-portfolio: digital experience

Observations/Personal Notes

Students like this activity a lot. It's important to give them enough time to explore and to create with autonomy.

37.- The sustainable city (Sabinianum Monselice, SDn Giuseppe Val Brembo)

Age Average:	9-11		Teaching Hours:	6	
Subjects	S	T	E	A	M
Others: Citizenship education, global perspectives, languages (Italian and English)					
Curricular	II	EC	DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D
Others:					
Instruction	AL	PBL	PLIE	SL	CL DTM IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this unit, the student will learn about renewable energy sources and will subsequently be invited to plan their use in the service of society. They will design and build a scale model of a sustainable city using Lego Spike Essentials and recycled materials.

2. Materials/Resources

- Stationery materials.
- Recycled materials (pizza boxes, glasses, plates, bottles, etc.).
- Lego Spike.
- iPad or Android Tablet.
- Any links and resources on the Internet.

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about the cells: cellular transport, types of cells, structures and functions, and unicellular organisms.
- Develop scientific inquiry skills, by making sense of an experience or answer a question using evidence and scientific understanding.
- Develop practical skills that include good observation, measurement, and equipment handling skills so that learners can collect accurate and reliable data.
- Use a compound microscope.
- Prepare a dry mount slide.
- Increase students’ problem-solving abilities.
- Practice cooperating positively.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: We’ll start with a video making us questions about animal cell function and plant cell function through a variety of approaches (active investigation, discussion, listening, reading...). They will start defining cells and looking at how cells interact with their environments through cellular transport.
- Session 2: Next, students look at the differences between prokaryotic and eukaryotic cells and then study the structures and functions of the organelles in these cells. Use QuiverApp (Augmented reality) as review.

- Session 3: Observation at the microscope. The unit content ends with a comparison of plant and animal cells and a look at how unicellular organisms carry out all life functions with just one cell.
- Session 4-6: Create a digital experience laboratory book (e-portfolio).
- Session 5-6: Create a 3D model of plant and animal cells with recycled materials.
- Session 6: Share it with a short presentation to the mates. Evaluation.

5. Results/Evidence

- 3D cells model with recycled materials (photos).
- E-portfolio: digital experience lab book (including photo, video...).

Observations/Personal Notes

Students like this activity a lot. It's important to give them enough time to explore and to create with autonomy.

38.- Solar System (Figlie di San Giuseppe, Rome, and Santa Sofia, Civitavecchia)

Age Average:	9-11		Teaching Hours:	8-12		
Subjects	S	T	E	A	M	Others:
Curricular	II	EC	DG	Diversity GAP		G I E R D Others: Cultural factor
Instruction	AL	PBL	PLIE	SL	CL	DTM IBL T Other: Learning by doing, problem-solving, inclusive environment

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn about the Solar System with the help of new technologies and 3D models. We'll learn the types of planets, structures, and functions of the planets. The student will learn to use Lego Spike.

2. Materials/Resources

- Solar System Lesson (147): (147) Lezione scienze sul Sistema solare per 5° elementare - YouTube and (147) Solar system - Wedo Lego - YouTube
- Lego Spike Introduction: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q1EFBSq_lbs

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

3. Learning Objectives

- Acquisition of new concepts and new learning methods.
- Develop practical skills that include good observation, measurement, and equipment handling skills so that learners can collect accurate and reliable data. - Conception and implementation of the construction of the individual planets, based on the concepts displayed in the previously prepared signage.
- Knowing how to experiment with material objects and with new tools and technological devices.
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Practice cooperating positively.
- Knowing how to observe and experiment in the field.
- Develop simple schematizations, modeling, logical formalizations, and Mathematical.
- Evaluate the position of objects in physical space, both for the subject and to other people.

- Addressing the concept of distance and measurement in an astronomical context in particular referring to the Solar System.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: We'll start with a presentation through a variety of approaches: brainstorming, circle time, active investigation, discussion, listening, and reading and we'll share videos. They will start defining planets and looking at how planets interact. Feedback.
- Session 2: Next, students look at the differences between the characteristics, structures, and functions of the planets. Final quiz.
- Session 3: Students will visit the Planetarium and Astronomical Museum and final report.
- Session 4-5: Create a 3D model of the planet with recycled materials. Self-evaluation.
- Session 6-7: Create a digital experience laboratory with Lego Spike. Self-evaluation.
- Session 8: Share it with a short presentation to the mates. Self-evaluation.

5. Results/Evidence

- 3D planets model with recycled materials (photos).
- E-portfolio: digital experience lab book (including photo, video...).

Observations/Personal Notes

Students like this activity a lot. It's important to give them enough time to explore and to create with autonomy. The intent is to stimulate curiosity.

39.- Shape a poem (Mons. E. Manfredini)

Age Average:	10-11		Teaching Hours:	35							
Subjects	S	T	E	A	M	Others: English, Music, Literature					
Curricular	II	EC	DG	Diversity GAP		G	I	E	R	D	Others: Learning Styles
Instruction	AL		PBL	PLIE	SL	CL	DTM	IBL	T	Other:	

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

Starting from a poem already read in class, the students will render its atmosphere and landscape graphically using Scratch.

2. Materials/Resources

- Literature book and worksheets.
- iPad or Windows PC, projector.
- Artistic elements and supports.
- Musical instruments.
- Scrap materials.
- Scratch.
- Wifi connection.

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn how to give commands in English (conceptual).
- Learn block programming language (conceptual).
- Use materials and techniques, that they have already learned, to build and create a “project” (procedural).
- Reading comprehension and work on the lexis (conceptual).
- Represent objects and concepts (procedural).
- Increase students’ problem-solving abilities (attitudinal).
- Practice cooperating positively (attitudinal).

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1:
 - Math: flow chart:
 - Introduction to the symbols of flow charts.
 - Creation of flow charts regarding real-life situations.
 - English: give commands:
 - The imperative form.
 - Vocabulary related to Scratch and coding.

- Practical activity: plan with a flow chart and create a course giving commands in English in groups.
- Session 2: Technology:
 - Block programming language:
 - Introduction to block programming language using Scratch.
 - Exercises.
- Session 3:
 - Literature: Reading comprehension and work on the lexis:
 - Group work: analysis of a poem and its figurative language.
 - Lexis analysis of the poems.
 - Art: representation of objects and concepts:
 - Representation of natural and figurative elements taken from the poems, using scrap materials.
 - Music: sounds of nature:
 - Representation of natural and figurative elements taken from the poems, recording the sounds created by the students with musical instruments and DIY instruments.

5. Results/Evidence

- Math and English: final joint activity (creation of a course).
- Technology: final product on Scratch.
- Arts: life drawing panel.
- Given the collaborative nature of the activity, we will distinguish between an evaluation of the product (group) and of the learning outcomes (personal), considering the attitudinal skills.

Observations/Personal Notes

Teachers have found trouble coordinating the activities, given the number of classes (5) and students (115).

40.- Geometrical Transformations (Collegio Bianconi – Sc. Cappelletti Turco)

Age Average:	11-12		Teaching Hours:	6		
Subjects	S	T	E	A	M	Others: Music
Curricular	II	EC	DG	Diversity GAP		G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL	PBL	PLIE	SL	CL	DTM IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn about geometrical transformations and the use of the same language in art and music.

2. Materials/Resources

- iPad or Android Tablet.
- Visual programming: Scratch.
- Recycled materials

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1uoMSk5iH290wObVjJ53B6PcFIREkZxsO/view?usp=sharing> (friezes)
- <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1X1wuE1psK45GwhBMbxm-JgO5qowDHyYr>

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about geometrical transformations: translations, symmetries, and similarity.
- Connect mathematical language with art and music using the same structure.
- Develop practical skills that include good observation, and measurement.
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Practice positively cooperating in pairs.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1 (1 hour):
 - We'll start with a video making us questions about which kind of transformations they can recognize (active investigation, discussion, listening, ...)
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PfoZq9WieZA>
 - Brainstorming: they will start making a list of observed transformations and watching again the video they will also identify the ones lost.
 - Teacher will explain how mathematical language is represented in repetitive artistic elements and in musical phrases (images in the file)

- Session 2 (2 hours): They will practice an exercise prepared using scratch about geometrical translation <https://scratch.mit.edu/projects/650415673>.
 - They will start a new Scratch project:
 - Challenge 1: create shapes in the plan (use the extension “Pen”; see an example <https://youtu.be/x6UZW5U0XeE>).
 - Challenge 2: create a new sprite and import it in Scratch. This sprite is the artistic element (to remove the background <https://youtu.be/Za0eJwV8jvk>).
 - Challenge 3: Connect the same geometrical shapes with the artistic element (see an example <https://scratch.mit.edu/projects/598337951>).
 - Challenge 4: Choose a sound in Scratch that matches the artistic element.
 - Challenge 5: Connect the sound to the artistic element.
- Session 3 (1 hour):
 - Challenge 6. Geometric similarity: focus on changing the size of shapes in the plan, changing the color of the corresponding artistic element, and modifying bpm in music.
- Session 4 (1 hour):
 - Final Test: Each pair will receive a different phrase with repetitions (A A) or variations (A A1) and will start a new Scratch project to translate it through the practiced languages.
- Session 5 (1 hour):
 - Share the project with the other pairs.

5. Results/Evidence

Scratch project during the final test

Observations/Personal Notes

It's important to give them enough time to explore and to create with autonomy.

Additional improvement: students can increase their knowledge of this universal language by building some artistic friezes with recycled materials and/or by inventing a piece of music with repetitions.

41.- Circuits and energy (Flaminia Di Rienzo secondary school)

Age Average:	16		Teaching Hours:	6		
Subjects	S	T	E	A	M	Others: Physics
Curricular	II	EC	DG	Diversity GAP		G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL	PBL	PLIE	SL	CL	DTM IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn about circuits with the help of new technologies. We'll learn about circuit components, conductors and insulators, different types of energy, and their transformation (focus on electrical to mechanical), from the agenda2030 renewable energy and environmental sustainability.

2. Materials/Resources

- iPad or Android Tablet.
- Makey Makey.
- Scratch.
- Micro:bit kit.
- Slides and video.

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-GVI8k1vtRE>
- <https://makecode.microbit.org/projects/banana-keyboard>
- <https://makecode.microbit.org/projects/banana-keyboard/maker>

2 b) Materials/Resources - Documents (optional)

- <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1ob4fjirSGjlu3H08igchZFYvGdFYZ5P9>
- <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1CFpUyOj6qtvaMlpBe5qpuhFqyZn32CmP>
- https://drive.google.com/open?id=1nGaXA4v_6_iLDzSHCRgPN0iHYFYqJPzv
- https://drive.google.com/open?id=1_82tQilQVU-goDEzArCa1ThGE7ks9ZAM

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about the circuit: circuit's components, conductor and insulators, different types of energy and its transformation (focus on electrical to mechanical), from the agenda2030 renewable energy and environmental sustainability.
- Learn about technology and coding.
- Develop scientific inquiry skills, by making sense of an experience or answer a question using evidence and scientific understanding.

- Develop practical skills that include good observation, and equipment handling skills so that learners can collect accurate and reliable data.
- Use an iPad or Android Tablet, Makey Makey, Scratch, Micro:bit kit
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Practice cooperating positively.
- Learn by doing, accept the mistake and recognize the importance of mistaken.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1 (1h): The teacher creates groups of 2/3 students. We'll start with a video to raise questions and student curiosity about circuits. Video link is: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-GVI8k1vtRE>. Next, students create the circuits using makey makey and any conducting object. The lessons will end with a brainstorming activity of the students thinking over the lesson.
- Session 2 (2h): The teacher presents scratch to the students. Next, the teacher asks the students to create an animation showing how electricity behaves in a circuit (with an insulator or a conductor) to fix the concepts. At the end of the lesson, they present to the class their scratch.
- Session 3 (2h): The teacher explains the different types of energy and the transformation and presents Micro:bit to the students. The teacher propose Micro:bit to create a circuit with a fan to show how energy transforms.

5. Results/Evidence

In an hour, giving the students the instruments, they can create a circuit based on what they have learned, and if they want they can use creativity to make something new. They have to make a video out of it and the teacher can evaluate it.

Observations/Personal Notes

42.- Every drop counts (Istituto Gesu e Maria)

Age Average:	11-14	Teaching Hours:	11
Subjects	S T E A M	Others: Informatics	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL	DTM IBL T	Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn about protecting, restoring, and promoting the sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems through the construction of a sustainable water system.

2. Materials/Resources

- Lab materials: jar, tools, soil.
- iPad or Android Tablet or computer.
- Micro_bit.
- Recycled materials.

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SGvCaV3lIfw>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jANCdtkJAKY>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rv4lb-U9QUU>

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about Agenda 2030: sustainable development goals 6 (sustainable management of water) and 15 (sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems to combat desertification).
- Learn about the efficient use of irrigation water.
- Develop practical skills that include building an irrigation system.
- Use Micro:bit.
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Practice cooperating positively.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1 (2 hours): We'll start with a lesson on the 2030 Agenda focusing on Goals 6 and 15. We discuss how important is to ensure the availability and sustainable management of water and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems to combat desertification.
- Session 2 (2 hours): Next, students go into the garden and experience contact with the soil and with everything that grows in it, through planting, water, and care.

- Session 3 (2 hours): Learn the history of irrigation systems, the best design to prevent even the smallest waste of water, and use sustainable materials.
- Session 4 (2 hours): Students learn to use Micro:bit technology
- Session 5 (2 hours): Use Micro:bit to create a sustainable irrigation system
- Session 6 (1 hour): Share it with a short presentation to the mates. Evaluation.

5. Results/Evidence

The construction of the water system.

Observations/Personal Notes

Students like this activity a lot. Its important to give them enough time to explore and to create with autonomy.

43.- Watch your steps (Bursa İnovasyon Merkezi (Bursa Innovation Centre))

Age Average:	11-14	Teaching Hours:	2
Subjects	S T E A M	Others: Language (Turkish)	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL	PLIE SL CL DTM IBL T	Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will explore kinetic energy during a movement at a constant speed. Students will:

- Learn to recognize the number of steps taken, as shown in an acceleration graph over time.
- Convert step count into average speed and average kinetic energy when walking.

2. Materials/Resources

- LEGO® Education SPIKE™ Prime Set
- Device with the LEGO Education SPIKE App installed
 - <https://education.lego.com/en-us/lessons/prime-training-trackers/watch-your-steps#engage>
 - <https://education.lego.com/en-us/lessons/prime-training-trackers/watch-your-steps/student-worksheet>

2. a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- https://education.lego.com/v3/assets/blt293eea581807678a/blt602fec21c66a1dfc/5f31039d7ca22b018aed80ee/45678_pedometer_book1.pdf
- https://education.lego.com/v3/assets/blt293eea581807678a/blt083b1c8d889d946d/5f3103ee0269427af13892f8/45678_pedometer_book2.pdf
- <https://education.lego.com/en-us/lessons/prime-training-trackers/watch-your-steps#engage>

3. Learning Objectives

Students will:

- Learn to recognize the number of steps taken, as shown in an acceleration graph over time.
- Convert step count into average speed and average kinetic energy when walking.
- Program a device to log data on a line graph.
- Interpret the values coming from the line graph.
- Explain kinetic energy about speed.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Engage (Before Class, 20 Min). This lesson explores the kinetic energy of a person walking at a constant speed. Your students will start by measuring the number of steps they've taken. They'll use that value to calculate the distance traveled, average walking speed, and average kinetic energy value for that motion. The Hub has an internal accelerometer that can detect movement on the 3 axes (i.e., up-down, left-right, front-back). When the Hub is clipped to someone's hip, it moves as they walk and records acceleration values. The resulting graph shows the minimum and maximum values of the recorded acceleration values. The precision of these minimum and maximum values will depend on the vertical position of the Hub while the student is walking. The "step count" precision will depend on the quality of these minimum and maximum values, and the calibrating values used in the program. Use various materials to engage your students on the topic of kinetic energy.

- Explore (In Class, 30 Min): Have your students build a pedometer that can count the number of steps taken. They can create their models, or follow the building instructions in the app to build the Pedometer model. Ask your students to try out their models using the suggested program. Tell them to look at the graph of acceleration over time, and describe what a "step" is.

- Explain (In Class, 15 Min.): Allow your students some time to adjust their programs to improve performance. Encourage them to record as much data as possible during their experiments. Have them export their data as a CSV file, so they can manipulate it in other software if they wish.

- Elaborate (After Class, 25 Min.): If your students still have access to their SPIKE Prime Sets, have them complete the tasks from the SPIKE App, to elaborate with hands-on learning, for example:
 - Ask them to illustrate their kinetic energy as they walk or as part of their program. They can use the docking station as one device to program to accomplish this task.
 - If your students don't have access to their sets, have them complete their Student Inventor Notebook, or assign one of the extension activities suggested below. Most of the extension activities can be done using the data collected during the hands-on session
 - Facilitate a sharing session in which your students exchange information. This can be done using whichever method/tool is most efficient (i.e., in-person or online).

- Evaluate: Give feedback on each student's performance. You can use the assessment rubrics provided to simplify the process.

5. Results/Evidence

- Individually collected information.
- E-portfolio: digital experience lab book (including photo, video...).
- The final product.

Observations/Personal Notes

Students fully accomplished all the phases, They worked collaboratively and in a harmony. They were very motivated and enthusiastic about the process and knowledge obtained during the activity.

44.- Moves and Turns (Özel Mesafe Mesleki ve Teknik Anadolu Lisesi)

Age Average:	13-15	Teaching Hours:	2
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL	CL DTM IBL T	Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this unit plan students will learn how to execute controlled movements (e.g., straight move, point turn, curved move) using a Driving Base

2. Materials/Resources

- LEGO® MINDSTORMS® Education EV3 Core Set.
- Laptop.
- EV3 Classroom App.

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- <https://education.lego.com/v3/assets/blt293eea581807678a/bltddb0d9e7188f73df5/5ec7bfb29b2ffb61d5c8091a/ev3-rem-driving-base.pdf>
- <https://education.lego.com/en-us/lessons/ev3-robot-trainer/1-moves-and-turns#lesson-plan>

2 b) Materials/Resources - Documents (optional)

- <https://education.lego.com/v3/assets/blt293eea581807678a/bltddb0d9e7188f73df5/5ec7bfb29b2ffb61d5c8091a/ev3-rem-driving-base.pdf>

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn the logic of algorithms, and activating sets according to the imagination.
- Learn how to execute controlled movements (e.g., straight move, point turn, curved move) using a Driving Base.
- Learn the basics of programming, and stack appropriate Move Blocks together to create programs.
- Design a prototype.
- Select appropriate blocks for making controlled movements.
- Change the parameters of blocks in iterative ways.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Prepare: Read through the student material in the EV3 Classroom App. Collect some information about encoded motors and how they're used in wheeled robots. You'll need a measuring tape to measure how far

the Driving Base drives. If you feel it's needed, plan a lesson using the "getting started" material in the app. This will help familiarize your students with LEGO® MINDSTORMS® Education EV3. To complete this lesson, the students will have to have built the Driving Base model from the Get Moving "getting started" activity, which will take about 30 minutes.

- Engage (10 Min.): Watch the unit video and use the ideas in the Ignite a Discussion section below to engage your students in a discussion related to this unit and lesson. Split your class into pairs.

- Explore (15 Min.): Allow your students some time to use the programming stacks provided to explore the movement of the Driving Base. Ask them to describe the different turns they've observed. Let them rearrange the programming stacks to explore the different movements.

- Explain (10 Min.): Facilitate a discussion about the importance of planning each step of a program. Explain what pseudocode is and how it can help your students as they plan their programs.

- Elaborate (10 Min.): Have your students find a way to move their Driving Base for 84 cm/33 in. Don't forget to leave some time for cleanup.
- Evaluate: Give feedback on each student's performance. You can use the assessment rubrics provided to simplify the process.

5. Results/Evidence

Students fully completed the instructions and enjoyed working as a group. The activity raised awareness for Steam areas. They are fully looking forward to proving themselves for the next lessons. They dreamed and improved ideas about using these experiences for real-world problems and social issues

Observations/Personal Notes

Differentiation. Simplify this lesson by spending extra time explaining what's being controlled by each parameter of the programming blocks

Take this lesson to the next level by having the students program the Driving Base to trace out a figure eight, the first letter of their name, or another letter or number

Making an obstacle course that requires the use of different turning methods to complete it.

45.- Airplane propeller (Bursa Ozel Cagdas Oncu Okulu)

Age Average:	10-11	Teaching Hours:	3								
Subjects	S	T	E	A	M	Others:					
Curricular	II	EC	DG	Diversity GAP		G	I	E	R	D	Others:
Instruction	AL	PBL	PLIE	SL	CL	DTM	IBL	T	Other:		

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will be able to design an airplane propeller with a simple electrical circuit and motor.

2. Materials/Resources

- Wooden sticks.
- Ping-pong balls.
- Glue gun.
- Paint.
- Simple electrical circuit.
- Battery.
- Switch.
- Cables.
- Motor.
- Propeller.
- Embellishment: pompoms, strips, crayons.

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1B974SRQo9LWeTdgMQs57k47PTdonziiR/edit>

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=c0R3gOMSIhE>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hxOpffM0bPg>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BwS6ySdHLpo&t=8s>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MSRucz59PEw>

3. Learning Objectives

- Makes body design from wooden sticks.
- Understands the logic of the simple electrical circuit.
- Makes the connections of the cables correctly.
- Sets up a simple electric circuit with a motor.
- It drives the propeller.
- Recognize the effects of friction force.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: Painting wooden sticks.
- Session 2: Makes a body design from wooden sticks.
- Session 3: Designs the fuselage of the aircraft model.
- Session 4: Simple electrical circuit components and logic are discussed.
- Session 5: It correctly connects the simple electrical circuit, starts the engine, and connects the propeller.
- Session 6: Tests the model. Discuss the effects of friction force.
 - https://drive.google.com/file/d/1y_9JzeWpfNUurqXFEFiLxSYicUPesDOP/view?usp=sharing

5. Results/Evidence

- Students designed and painted an airplane model and made circuit connections. They also discussed the effect of frictional force. Thus, the permanence of learning by doing was ensured by using all areas of STEAM. (photos).
- E-portfolio: digital experience lab book (including photo, video...).

Observations/Personal Notes

With an interdisciplinary study, we designed an activity about electrical connections, conversion of energy into motion, and design following the main idea of CreaSTEAM. We brought interest in STEAM.

46.- The future of sustainability on the CBES (Clemens-Brentano-Europeschule Lollar)

Age Average:	15-16	Teaching Hours:	20							
Subjects	S	T	E	A	M	Others: Social sciences, politics				
Curricular	II	EC	DG	Diversity GAP	G	I	E	R	D	Others:
Instruction	AL	PBL	PLIE	SL	CL	DTM	IBL	T	Other:	

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

- Basic knowledge about climate change on the scientific and social science side.
- Application of knowledge related to school.
- Planning a project to implement knowledge about sustainability in various areas, if possible at school.

2. Materials/Resources

- Future boxes.
- Climate case.
- Computers.
- Smartphones.
- Woodworking tools.
- 3D-Printers.

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- <https://klimawandel-schule.de/de/der-lmu-klimakoffer>
- <https://futurium.de/de/bildung-und-vermittlung/zukunftsbox>

3. Learning Objectives

- Work together.
- Solve problems.
- Build.
- Experiment.
- Plan.
- Implement.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Working with the future boxes to obtain basic knowledge about sustainability in various areas.
- Sustainable city tour.
- Working with the climate case to obtain basic knowledge about climate change.

- Research on the current status of sustainability and climate protection at our school.
- Planning projects to improve sustainability and climate protection at our school.

5. Results/Evidence

- Test on basic knowledge related to sustainability and climate change.
- Planning status and development progress of the projects.

Observations/Personal Notes

47.- Easy energy. Different types of energy in Micro:bit (Luzzago high school, Brescia)

Age Average:	15-16	Teaching Hours:	6
Subjects	S T E A M	Others: Civics, Physics	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL DTM IBL T	Other:	

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn about the different types of energy with a focus on the new energy sources. They will learn about this topic with the use of Micro Bit, so they can learn dynamically.

2. Materials/Resources

- Lab materials: Kitronik inventor’s kit and Micro Bit.
- iPad, Android Tablet, or personal computer.
- Video application example: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PSStp1KmZ2U>

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- Micro Bit code examples: <https://microbit.org/projects/make-it-code-it/>
- Hot to use an Inventor’s Micro Bit Kit: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lmdzM74XyHw>
- Different types of energy: <https://www.enelgreenpower.com/it/learning-hub/transizione-energetica/fonti-rinnovabili>

2 b) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about different types of energy and use modality.
- Focus on the importance of renewable energies regarding climate change (goal 7 of the 2030 agenda) and the economic situation of Italy.

- Develop technological inquiry skills, by making experiments with Micro:bit.
- Develop practical skills that include good observation and equipment handling skills so that learners can understand different types of energy.
- Use and code Micro:bit inventor's kit.
- Prepare a subtitled video tutorial with an oral explanation of the experiment.
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Practice cooperating positively and to work in a team.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: We'll start with a brainstorming lesson. We'll give post-it to students and we'll split the whiteboard into three parts with the different following questions:
 - What is renewable energy?
 - Which type of renewable energy do you know?
 - Which type of renewable energy do you use in your ordinary life?
 - Then, we'll discuss answers.
- Session 2: we'll introduce Micro:bit and we'll give an Inventor's Kit to each student group. Then, we'll ask students to do a simple code, such as showing a smile.
- Session 3: students have to work in a group to code a light bulb ignition.
- Session 4: students have to think about a different type of energy and choose two of them (one renewable and one not) to repeat the experiment in session 3.
- Session 5: students have to prepare a subtitled video tutorial with an oral explanation of the experiment.
- Session 6: share it with a short explanation to the mates. Evaluation.

5. Results/Evidence

Exeriment (photos), and video tutorial.

Observations/Personal Notes

Students may like this activity because they can experiment.

48.- The 3D Renaissance (Liceo Luzzago, Istituto Salesiano Sacri Couri, and Istituto Gesu e Maria)

Age Average:	16-17	Teaching Hours:	12								
Subjects	S	T	E	A	M	Others: Geometry					
Curricular	II	EC	DG	Diversity	GAP	G	I	E	R	D	Others:
Instruction	AL	PBL	PLIE	SL	CL	DTM	IBL	T	Other:		

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this unit, the student's goal is to create an archive of tactile tools (3D library) concerning paintings from the Renaissance period, using three-dimensional drawing and 3D printing as technology. For each painting, they should recognize the geometric composition, and any natural elements to be analyzed.

Among the final goals, there is another specific one that's to create an online open-source archive through which other entities (other schools, classes) can use the files to print.

The unit will end with an exhibition by the students of their projects created. They also create and update daily their diary describing the project.

2. Materials/Resources

- Lab materials: artistic material, 3D printer.
- Computer\Tablet.
- Software Tinkercad.
- Recycled materials.

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- Tutorial Tinkercad: <https://of3lia.com/tinkercad-tutorial-completo/>
- If the school hasn't a 3D printer they can use this site: <https://www.shapeways.com/>
- For research on biology use app: <https://www.inaturalist.org/>

2 b) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about the knowledge about art: composition, use of colors in the picture, information about the period, and the artist.
- Learn about the science knowledge: systematic system to classify animals and plants, and description of each species with its peculiar characteristic.
- Learn about the knowledge about geometry: recognize geometric shapes and associate them with the typology.
- Learn the knowledge about informatics: main software tools and digital skills.
- Create prototype texture to understand the effectiveness of touch.
- Use a computer and a 3D printer.
- Write a journey diary.
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Practice cooperating in a positive way

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1 (1 Hour): the students develop the test on Google forms and with this information, we can create balance groups with different abilities. Each group creates in google classroom a journey diary day, at the start of lessons each group talks for one minute about the update of their journey diary to the class.
- Session 2 (2 hours): students start to research an artwork in the historical period chosen and they analyze and understand how people with blindness relate to the world around them.
- Session 3 (2 hours): During the Art- lab time the student will try to understand the main shapes and try to make a simplified version of the artwork.
- Session 4 (1 Hour): the students find and recognize the principal living organism in the chosen opera. They have to classify the animals or the plants, with a single schedule that described the taxonomy and the peculiar characteristic and behavior of the species in the chosen opera.
- Session 5-6 (3 hours): introduction to the software “Tinkercard” and view of the tutorial with exercises finally create a model and start printing.

- Session 6 (2 Hours): The student does the initial google form test again and they show their projects with a blind exhibition where the visitors touch the 3D printing to recognize the opera and the elements, the blind exhibition is a secret for the class before the activities.

5. Results/Evidence

Blind exhibition and a journey diary.

Observations/Personal Notes

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49.- Make your energy (Collegio Bianconi, and Istituto Tecnico Industriale “Don Luigi Orione”)

Age Average:	9				Teaching Hours:	5					
Subjects	S	T	E	A	M	Others: Physics, civil education					
Curricular	II	EC	DG	Diversity GAP		G	I	E	R	D	Others:
Instruction	AL	PBL	PLIE	SL	CL	DTM	IBL	T	Other:		

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn about renewable energies with the help of new technologies and interactive models. They'll learn the difference between the sources of energy and will create their power station, making a comparison between renewable and non-renewable energies. They'll have the chance to simulate how a power station works, seeing the functioning in practice.

The project may be simplified for primary students.

2. Materials/Resources

- Lab materials: Lego Mindstorm EV3, Micro:bit, Kitronic Inventor’s Kit expansion.
- Tablet/computer.
- Recycled materials.
- Colored pencils.
- Felt-tips.

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- Lego windmill: <https://education.lego.com/en-us/lessons/spm/windmill>
- Micro:bit wind turbine: shorturl.at/ikoqZ

2 b) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

Example of non-renewable energy

Example of a photovoltaic power station

Eolic power station

Final project

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about renewable energies: eolic energy, hydroelectric energy, geothermal energy, and photovoltaic energy.
- Learn about the difference between renewable and non-renewable energies.
- Develop a practical skill.
- Develop electronic skills.
- Develop coding skills.
- Improve team working and cooperation skills.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 0: Creation of groups of 3 students. The choice of the students is random, to avoid preferences based on gender, disabilities, or origin. Some adjustments will be made, focusing only on their skills.
- Session 1 (60 mins): brief revision about the different sources of energy previously studied, possibly supported by video materials.
- Session 2 (90 mins): each group of students will create its power station. The stations will be picked randomly (among non-renewable, eolic, hydroelectric, geothermal, and photovoltaic power stations). Each student will have a role (picked randomly): programmer, head of construction, and scientist.
- Session 3 (45 mins): discussion of the results. Comparison between the different works. Focus on the renewable power stations: the non-renewable one will stop after a while, and the other will continue working.
- Session 4 (90 mins): every group tries to replicate the project of another group. The students' roles previously assigned are switched.

5. Results/Evidence

- Small models of the different power stations.
- Portfolio (for students from 9 to 14 years old):
 - Drawing and schemes of the project with a brief explanation.
- E-portfolio (for 13+ years old students):
 - It may also include photos and videos for the upper secondary students.

The workshop and the portfolios will be evaluated by the teacher to have feedback about the experience: cooperation and commitment of the students will be taken into account too.

Observations/Personal Notes

50.- Tectonic plates (Istituto Tecnico Industriale “Don Luigi Orione”, and Liceo Luzzago)

Age Average:	14-18	Teaching Hours:	6
Subjects	S T E A M	Others: Geology, politics, informatics	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL	CL DTM IBL T	Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn about Tectonic Plates Theory. During this unit, the students try to simulate what happens when two continental crusts crush each other. At the end of the experience, students will be able to make a hypothesis about the movements of the real plates.

2. Materials/Resources

- Lab materials:
 - Polystyren.
 - Aluminum film.
 - Paper mache.
 - Cardboard.
 - Glue.
 - Colors.
- iPad or Android Tablet.
- Lego Mindstorms EV3.
- Computer.
- Recycled materials (plastic, paper, tissue, wood, biological materials)

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fUuG_wTlocE
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8rALMfsgkdA>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4OxcrUzFQEg>

2 b) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about the movements of the tectonic plates: General basics knowledge of the main tectonic mechanisms and integration of different approaches (e.g. structural geology, metamorphism) in understanding the geodynamic evolution of an orogen
- Develop scientific inquiry skills, by making sense of an experience or answer a question using evidence and scientific understanding.
- Develop practical skills that include good observation, measurement, and equipment handling skills so that learners can collect accurate and reliable data.
- Use Lego Mindstorms EV3.
- Prepare the two robots and the models.
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Practice cooperating positively.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1 (2h): We'll start with a video making us questions about tectonic movements and orogen (active investigation, discussion, listening, reading...):
 - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fUuG_wTlocE.
 - They will start defining plates, movement physics laws, terrestrial stratification, and density.
- Session 2a (1h informatics lab, more time optional at home): Design the robots; design Lego Mindstorms EV3.
- Session 2b (2 h lab, more time optional at home): Design the plates prototype using every kind of material.
- Session 3 (at home): Create a digital experience laboratory book (e-portfolio).
- Session 4 (1h, classroom): Share it with a short presentation to the mates. Evaluation.

5. Results/Evidence

- Tectonic plates prototype (photos)
- E-portfolio: digital experience lab book (including photo, video...)
- Final test about results

Observations/Personal Notes

51.- A glimpse across time (Liceo Scienze Applicate, Rome)

Age Average:	15-16	Teaching Hours:	5
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	ICT, languages (English)
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity	GAP G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL	CL DTM	IBL T Other: Flipped Classroom

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, the students will practice using Scratch and develop a template for a timeline. The class will be divided into groups and the best template will then be shared with the rest of the class. Then, this timeline will be used in other classes to help SEN students with their curricular subjects. We imagined a possible use with English culture, in particular with the Renaissance.

2. Materials/Resources

- Scratch.
- Computers.
- iPad or Android tablet
- Textbooks.
- Websites.

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- Tutorial of Scratch: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VGz6DpjNpBw>
- Link to timeline: <https://scratch.mit.edu/projects/749005864>

ASSESSMENT RUBRIC FOR A TIMELINE				
Student's name: _____				
ASPECTS	4 EXCELLENT	3 GOOD	2 NEED IMPROVEMENT	1 LOW PERFORMANCE
Documentation of Events	The timeline contains all 10 significant events. This includes date, description and picture	The timeline contains at least 8-9 significant events. This includes date, description and picture	The timeline contains at least 7 significant events. This includes date, description and picture	The timeline contains less than 5 significant events. This includes date, description and picture
Content/Facts	Facts were accurate for all events reported on the timeline.	Facts were accurate for almost all events reported on the timeline.	Facts were accurate for most (~75%) of the events reported on the timeline.	Facts were often inaccurate for the events that were reported on the timeline.
Accuracy	All dates indicated on timeline are correct and are sequenced in the proper order.	At least 8-9 of the dates are accurate or sequences are in the proper order.	At least 6-7 of the dates are accurate or sequences are in the proper order.	Less than 5 of the dates are accurate or sequences are in the proper order.
Documentation of Events	The timeline contains all 10 significant events. This includes date, description and picture	The timeline contains at least 8-9 significant events. This includes date, description and picture	The timeline contains at least 7 significant events. This includes date, description and picture	The timeline contains less than 5 significant events. This includes date, description and picture
Sentence Fluency	Events are clearly described using accurate and vivid language	Events are described well, but language is sometimes vague or inaccurate.	Events are not described well and language is often vague or inaccurate.	Events are described using vague language or inaccurate information.
Style & Organization	The timeline was set up to cover the relevant time period. It contains appropriate yearly gradations of set intervals	The timeline was set up to cover the relevant time period. It contains yearly gradations, but not at set intervals.	The timeline was set up to cover most of the relevant time period. It contains appropriate yearly gradations.	The time period covered was in appropriate. Yearly divisions were not uniform.
Mechanics	Punctuation, spelling, and capitalization were checked and are correct throughout.	Punctuation, spelling, and capitalization were checked and are mostly correct.	Punctuation, spelling, and capitalization are somewhat correct and may or may not have been checked.	There are many punctuation, spelling, and capitalization errors.

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about Scratch.
- Learn about the Renaissance and Shakespeare.
- Develop practical skills.
- Prepare a timeline to be used in class.
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities and learning abilities.
- Practice cooperating positively.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- **Session 1:** (flipped classroom, at home, estimated time 1 hour), the students are given some videos about how to use Scratch at home and have to come to class prepared. They still don't know what they will be asked to do with it.
- **Session 2:** warm-up activity with simple challenges on Scratch (15 min); presentation of the project and creation of the groups (15 mins); Tinkering (30 mins), the students experiment with the software and as a ticket-to-leave exercise they need to share a picture of their progress on Google Classroom.
- **Session 3:** (2 hours) realization of the timeline; the teacher supervises the work and gives feedback and help if needed. At the end of the lesson the class votes and decides on the best template which is shared with the entire class.
- **Session 4:** (1 hour) cooperation with the English teacher; the students are assigned some topics, such as the monarchs of the Tudor dynasty, Shakespeare's plays, Christopher Marlowe's plays, etc. from their book and spend some time producing the final product. (if they don't finish, give them as homework)
- **Session 5:** (1 hour) the students present their work to the teachers and receive feedback (formative assessment and self-assessment). They are encouraged to use the template for future use.

5. Results/Evidence

The timeline will be used as a form of portfolio for their future studies.

Observations/Personal Notes

Students like this activity a lot. It's important to give them enough time to explore and to create with autonomy.

52.- Me as a robot (Primary school San Giovanni Bosco, Cinecittà, Roma, and Primary school Monumento ai Caduti, Monserrato, Cagliari)

Age Average:	6-8	Teaching Hours:	15
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	Geography
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity	GAP G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL DTM		IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn about communicating the position of objects in physical space using appropriate terms, following simple paths starting from the verbal description or drawing, describing a path you are taking, and giving instructions to someone to follow the desired path. Know the computer in its structural functions, and recognize and document the main functions of a computer application.

2. Materials/Resources

- iPad, Android Tablet, or Computer.
- Scratch <https://scratch.mit.edu/>
- Blockly maze <https://blockly.games/maze>
- Paper, colored felt-tip-pens, colored scotch.

3. Learning Objectives

- Orient yourself within a structured space.
- Distinguish direction in a path.
- Move along paths, describe them and represent them graphically on a structured plan.
- Recognize and evaluate trajectories, distances, and execution rhythms, knowing how to organize one's movement in space about oneself, to objects, and others.
- Know the computer in its main functions, using specific programs.
- Develop practical skills that include good observation and equipment handling skills.
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Practice cooperating positively.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: Children will experience a path created by the teacher by becoming familiar with the directions (forward, backward, turn right, turn left).
- Session 2: The children will work in pairs, one behind the other, giving each other directions by pressing a button panel on their back.

- Session 3: On the IWB the teacher introduces the children to the program <https://blockly.games/maze> and together they solve the first two levels.
- Session 4: In the computer room, children in pairs will solve levels 3 and 4 of <https://blockly.games/maze>
- Session 5: On the IWB the teacher introduces the children to the Scratch program and together they create a simple path.
- Session 6: In the computer room, children in pairs, using the Scratch program, will reproduce a path requested by the teacher, then they will create a path they have designed and structured.
- Session 7: The children, in groups of 3, will propose the path they have created to their classmates: one child says the commands, one child physically executes them, and one child reproduces them on the Scratch program to compare the two paths corresponding.
- Session 8: In the computer room, the children, individually, will create a smile with the Scratch program that represents their degree of satisfaction with the path they have done.

5. Results/Evidence

Scratch path.

Observations/Personal Notes

53.- The Mov'it (Margherita Institute in Bari)

Age Average:	6-7	Teaching Hours:	6
Subjects	S T E A M	Others: Geography, physical education, social studies, languages	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL DTM IBL T	Other:	

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn about positioning with the help of new technologies and 3D models. We'll learn about topological issues.

2. Materials/Resources

- Lab materials, recycled materials, and school materials.
- iPad or Android Tablet.
- Education App: <https://lego.com>

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

3. Learning Objectives

- Learning about the child within the space: his/her position in the space, the ability to focus the attention on the surrounding space (details & in general), orienting oneself through reference points, using topological indicators (right, left, forward...).
- Developing inquiry skills, by making sense of an experience or answer a question using evidence and geographical understanding.
- Increasing students' problem-solving abilities.
- Positively practicing cooperative learning.
- Identifying the main functions of block programming.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: We'll start with a visit to the environments.
- Session 2: Next, ask the students to appoint environments first in Italian and then in English by creating flash cards.
- Session 3: Create environments through the use of recycled materials.
- Session 4: Create a map allowing the robot to move through the path.
- Session 5: Assemble the robot and program the path.
- Session 6: Create alternative paths and share the project in groups.

5. Results/Evidence

- A 3D model with recycled materials (photos).
- E-portfolio: digital experience lab book (including photo, video...).

Observations/Personal Notes

- Optional comments or recommendations.
- Self-evaluation.
- Students like this activity a lot. It's important to give them enough time to explore and to create with autonomy.

54.- Autobus or taxi? (Scuola primaria Vanzo, Padova)

Age Average:	9-10		Teaching Hours:	12		
Subjects	S	T	E	A	M	Others: Italian (Listening, speaking, reading), digital citizenship
Curricular	II	EC	DG	Diversity GAP		G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL	PBL	PLIE	SL	CL	DTM IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this learning unit, with the help of technology, students will learn how to move vehicles on a geographic grid by avoiding obstacles and finding solutions for specific needs. In this Unit Plan, students will learn to move the means of transport in a geographical grid, avoiding obstacles and finding a solution for specific needs, with the help of new technologies.

2. Materials/Resources

- Lab materials: Lego education spike set.
- iPad or Android Tablet with Lego education spike app.
- Recycled materials.
- Additional materials: poster board and stationery materials for various uses (brainstorming, rules, etc...)

3. Learning Objectives

- Identify and correct errors in a program and refine it to meet a specific need.
- Test and evaluate solutions to determine if they meet a specific need.
- Read and orient in maps and grids; explore shapes and angles.
- Relate an experience correctly and in detail.
- Use Lego Educational Spike devices and apps responsibly
- Increase problem-solving skills.
- Predict the consequences of personal decisions or behaviors.
- Know the rules of the highway code.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: Introduction of the lesson by brainstorming and subsequent viewing of a video regarding good practices on road traffic with discussion. In the end, possible solutions to the issues raised are proposed.
- Session 2: Pupils divided into pairs are asked to build a bus and a cab without receiving any instruction from the teacher. In the end, a discussion based on some questions: "does the constructed vehicle have the structure suitable to move?", "what could you add or modify?" Directing the discussion to the need to add an electronic component.
- Session 3: The teacher presents the class with the project for building cabs and buses using the Lego Spike Education application. The pupils proceed to the construction of the vehicles following the instructions and

subsequently programming the vehicle taking into consideration the grid to be used and the rules of the road (e.g. example, the bus must stop at the green stop).

- Session 4: Children try out the constructed and programmed means within the grid and modify the programming to correct any errors.
- Session 5: Pupils write a text explaining why it is important to have accessibility for all to public spaces (including people with disabilities)
- Session 6: Each group runs their device on the grid along with the other means and explains The various steps of construction and programming, the difficulties encountered, and the different programming.

5. Results/Evidence

Photos and videos about the session are shared on the classroom's platform.

Observations/Personal Notes

The teacher measures her pupils' competence in identifying and correcting errors in a program. The teacher creates a rating scale based on his or her own needs (e.g. Needs more support/can work independently/can teach others...).

Self-assessment: the teacher invites pupils to choose a brick that she thinks represents the quality of her work (yellow= I think I can identify and correct errors; blue= I can identify and correct errors; green=I can identify correct errors and know how to help others to do so).

55.- Responsible consumption and production (waste sorting and recycling (Scuola Primaria Maria Ausiliatrice, and Istituto Gesù Maria)

Age Average:	8-10	Teaching Hours:	6
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	civics, languages
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL CL	DTM IBL T	Other: Learning by doing

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, the students will learn about waste sorting and recycling with the help of Robotics (Lego Spike). They'll develop knowledge about materials to sort and recycle and practical skills for good end ethical behavior (considering also Goal 12 of Agenda 2030). They'll also learn vocabulary and processes in the English language.

2. Materials/Resources

- Future boxes.
- Tablets/Computers.
- Materials to recycle (plastic bottles, papers, glass, organic).
- 2 Lego Spike Essential kits for each group.
- Colored stamps.

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- Online tutorial <https://spike.legoeducation.com/> in English – The Cable car adapted to a recycling process.
- Online game on Scratch website (<https://scratch.mit.edu/projects/387935555/>).
- Video about recycling (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6jQ7y_qQYUA) English language.

2 b) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about the basics of waste sorting: collect and sort wastes, and recognize different materials.
- Develop practical skills in responsible consumption and production.
- Develop knowledge about English vocabulary related to the topic.
- Learn about coding and programming (elementary level).
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Practice cooperating positively.
- Long life objective: shared taxonomy and behavior to achieve Goal 12 of Agenda 2030.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: We'll start with a video making us questions about waste sorting and recycling (video made by teachers) with a link to the Agenda 2030 (Goal 12). They will start defining different materials and understanding the importance of garbage sorting. Brainstorming about kids' personal experiences on garbage collection and recycling.
- Session 2: They will look at the differences between some materials brought by teachers and they start distinguishing and sorting materials by putting colored stamps on them (yellow for plastic, red for organic, blue for paper, and green for glass). They practice waste sorting by playing an online game (<https://scratch.mit.edu/projects/387935555/>) They'll play an English game (introduction to English vocabulary).
- Session 3: They build the structure with Lego Spike (they follow the online tutorial <https://spike.legoeducation.com/> in English – The Cable car + the teacher's tutorial)
- Session 4: They'll work on Lego Spike programming.
- Session 5: They will focus on the English vocabulary and the process of waste sorting. They'll watch a video about recycling (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6jQ7y_qQYUA) and then they'll do some exercises about English vocabulary (matching and cloze).
- Session 6: Share the acquired knowledge with a short presentation to the mates. Evaluation of digital competencies (programming skills) and English language skills (vocabulary and simple sentences to describe the recycling process).

5. Results/Evidence

- Lego Spike models created by children (photos)
- Children's presentations (including photos, and videos...)

Observations/Personal Notes

Students like this activity a lot. It's important to give them enough time to explore, create with autonomy and collaborate.

56.- Keeping the school clean (Istituto Sacro Cuore Carpi Modena)

Age Average:	9-11		Teaching Hours:	6		
Subjects	S	T	E	A	M	Others: Civics, geography
Curricular	II	EC	DG	Diversity GAP		G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL	PBL	PLIE	SL	CL	DTM IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this unit, we aim to offer education in caring for the environment in which one lives to internalize the importance of living in a clean environment. Using the environment means having resources available that benefit everyone in a community school. Therefore, the daily activities of each person spill over to everyone by also understanding the risks involved in bad behavior.

2. Materials/Resources

- Lab materials: slides, youtube, etc.
- iPad or Android Tablet.
- www quiz: <https://www.wwf.ch/it/vivere-sostenibile/calcolatore-dell-impronta-ecologica>

3. Learning Objectives

- Raise awareness of caring for the environment.
- Be open to respect for others.
- Learn to collaborate.
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Promote creativity.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Projection of school environments left messy and unclean.
- Discussion among the pupils: Inquiry.
- Brainstorming on possible consequences.
- Viewing selected videos to understand possible solutions.
- Debate on problem-solving.
- Voting on possible solutions to be adopted at school.
- Design and construction in two groups with Lego Spike.

5. Results/Evidence

Construction of a robot with functions consistent with the solutions thought up during the discussions.

57.- Cards in play (Sacro Cuore (Carpi), and Monumento ai Caduti (Monserrato))

Age Average:	5	Teaching Hours:	10
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	Languages
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL	CL DTM IBL T	Other: Learning by doing, peer tutoring, circle time, teamwork.

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this learning unit, children will enhance their knowledge of the graphic sign and phonemes through a playful approach using technology (Bee-Bot).

2. Materials/Resources

- Poster board
- Markers, ruler, tempera
- Bee-Bot

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

3. Learning Objectives

- Becoming familiar with the language, and developing its potential through materials and stimuli to enhance skills.
- Knowing how to distinguish a picture or drawing from writing.
- Sequential reading and word games.
- Using machines and technological tools, recognizing their functions and possible uses.
- Identifying the position of a letter in a space.
- Correctly follow a route based on others' or one's verbal indications.
- Play constructively and creatively with peers.
- Argue, confront and support one's reasons with adults and children.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: let's become robots: the children become robots, which will be programmed in turn by teachers and classmates to complete paths.
- Session 2: bee-bot presentation. the teacher shows the bee-bot, presents how it works, and gives children hands-on experience of its use.
- Session 3: activity explanation. The teacher presents the mat and gives the children instructions on how to carry out the route with the Bee-Bot, starting with letters and ending with the construction of words
- Session 4: activity on the mat with the Bee-Bot. The children program the Bee-Bot to reconstruct words indicated by the teacher, their classmates, or chosen by themselves.

5. Results/Evidence

- Photos.
- Video.
- Logbook.
- Impressions and feedback from the family.

Observations/Personal Notes

It is important to work first with the body and then with the instrument, giving adequate time for the children to get to know the Bee-Bot better. For the best success of the activity, small group work is recommended.

58.- Yes, we count! (Istituto Margherita (Bari), and Istituto “Paolo VI” (Chioggia))

Age Average:	5-6		Teaching Hours:	8						
Subjects	S	T	E	A	M	Others:				
Curricular	II	EC	DG	Diversity GAP	G	I	E	R	D	Others:
Instruction	AL	PBL	PLIE	SL	CL	DTM	IBL	T	Other:	

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will learn about numbers with the help of new technologies. We'll learn about the quantity concept, the sequence of numbers, and the discrimination of even and odd numbers.

2. Materials/Resources

- Flash cards.
- Recycled materials.
- Commonly used material (wood sticks, glue, tape, plasticine, colors, etc.).
- Tablet and LIM.

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

Model of the activity in class:

3. Learning Objectives

- Learn about the numbers: quantity concept, sequence of numbers, discrimination of even and odd numbers, and associate numbers to quantity.
- Develop inquiry skills, by making experiences about quantity and numbers.
- Develop practical skills that include good observation, measurement, and spatial orienting.
- Develop specific language.
- Develop the concept of sequence and computational thinking.
- Increase listening and give clear instructions.
- Increase cooperative learning.

- Prepare flash cards.
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities.
- Practice cooperating positively.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: We'll start with a laboratory with numbers. In this experience, children can think about the quantity and the sequence of numbers. They will start defining numbers and using materials in different quantities they have to associate the single quantity with the corresponding number.
- Session 2: Students made flash cards (with numbers and quantity) with paper and other materials. At the same time.
- Session 3: Realization of the numbers with the material of daily use.
- Session 4: Share it with a short presentation to the mates. Evaluation.

5. Results/Evidence

- Systematic observations.
- Photos and videos.
- Assessment of skills non-didactic.
- Project the activity built with Code.org.

Link: <https://studio.code.org/projects/spritelab/mTulRkymD7VQqQavoezqsAlg0UAdeikVq4OxUVBHsac?qr=true>

Observations/Personal Notes

59.- Everyone in the bathroom to wash their hands (Scuola dell’infanzia, Rome)

Age Average:	3-5	Teaching Hours:	2
Subjects	S T E A M	Others: Languages, sports	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE	SL CL	DTM IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this unit, children learn about the sequence of everyday gestures (washing hands) through play. In addition, older children experiment with coding using the Bee-bot.

2. Materials/Resources

- Bee-bot.
- Bathroom space.
- Grid.
- Flashcards with arrows and sequence images.

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

3. Learning Objectives

- For 3-years children:
 - Knowledge and reproduction of the sequence.
 - Learning the nursery rhyme.
- 4 years old:
 - Knowledge and reproduction of the sequence.
 - Learning the nursery rhyme.
 - Moving around following simple directions on the grid.
- 5 years old:
 - Kowing and reproducing the sequence.

- Learning the nursery rhyme.
- Making robots.
- Moving following simple indications on the grid.
- Laterality.
- Programming the sequences leading to the execution of the gesture (flashcards+arrows).
- Knowing how to use the Bee-bot.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1: introduction of activities in circle time with a reading of the book "I don't want to wash my hands" by Tony Ross, explanation of the following activities, and nursery rhyme:
 - "I open the tap slowly...
 - The water runs over my hand...
 - With a few drops of soap...
 - I create a foamy cloud...
 - I put my hands together in an embrace...
 - I rub once and do it again"
- Session 2: robot teacher.
- Session 3: big robot child.
- Session 4: grid is drawn on the floor with pictures of the sequence, differentiation by age.
 - >3 years, move freely in the grid reaching for the images indicated by the teacher. (indication: reach the image of the tap that opens, the soap..etc, so the child moves freely to reach the target).
 - >4 years old, they move around the squares of the grid, following a path guided by arrows to reach the drawings that make up the sequence.
 - >5 years: they plan the route to be taken on the grid on the ground using arrows. They move around the grid squares, following their path to reach the drawings that make up the sequence. Then, they prepare a paper grid with 15x15 cm squares on which they make the Bee-Bot move, after programming it.

5. Results/Evidence

- Video.
- Photos for posters and final exercise book.
- Children's work.

Observations/Personal Notes

This project aims to differentiate activities and objectives according to the age of the children. The structure of the project is designed to proceed step by step, giving priority to the corporeal, concrete, and practical dimension followed by a cognitive and abstract one. This methodology can also be applied to children with disabilities as the use of pecs and visual diaries helps them to acquire concepts and consequently autonomy or the scanning of events.

60.- Play through math (Middle School “V. Poloni”)

Age Average:	11-14	Teaching Hours:	8
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE	SL CL	DTM IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan, students will improve their mathematical skills by using technology to program a game based on calculation and algorithms. They'll develop basic logical foundations, problem-solving, and algorithmic skills.

Organization: Students will work in little groups: the pairs will be chosen by the teachers paying attention to their learning level, which will be the same for each pair, to fill the gap and to have the same starting point. This is an educational choice we made to prepare the finest learning atmosphere with a positive approach to the discipline. Moreover, we believe that, in this way, motivation and self-esteem would improve, upgrading learning skills.

2. Materials/Resources

- PC or Laptop.
- Android Tablet or iPad.
- Scratch education App: [Scratch - Imagine, Program, Share \(mit.edu\)](https://scratch.mit.edu)

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- Scratch guideline: [Getting-Started-Guide-Scratch2.pdf \(mit.edu\)](https://scratch.mit.edu/docs/2)
- Final project: <https://scratch.mit.edu/projects/767279642>

2 b) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

- For the teachers:
 - [Pedagogical Possibilities for the 2048 Puzzle Game \(gettysburg.edu\)](https://www.gettysburg.edu/~jgibson/2048/)
- For the students:

3. Learning Objectives

- Learning-by-doing: Learn about basic math, sums, multiplication, and the power of 2.
- Develop basic logical abilities, problem-solving competencies, and algorithmic skills.
- Develop practical skills including making a game based on a mathematical algorithm.
- Learn how to use Scratch to create useful applications.
- Develop the ability to apply mathematics to create a visible product.
- Increase students' problem-solving abilities and their self-esteem related to their skills and learning capacity.
- Practice cooperating positively.

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Session 1 (2 hours):
 - Part I: We'll start with a presentation that can help them understand how scratch works.
 - Part II: observe concrete examples you can find on the website and try to understand how the examples work and how they are implemented.
- Session 2 (2 hours):
 - Part I: Students will cooperate to review basic math concepts needed in the project (such as sums, multiplications, and power of 2).
 - Part II: Teachers will explain the basic algorithm of the game with the various steps and logical points.

- Session 3 (3 hours):

- Part I: Program your own game starting with the creation of the concrete project on Scratch, followed by the practical implementation of the game using block programming.
- Part II: Testing of the game and possible resolution of identified problems (making sure that everything is working properly).
- Part III: Auto-evaluation: take your time (at least 10 minutes) to reflect on your behavior and fill out the questionnaire you have in Classroom (see results/evidence section).
- Session 4 (1 hour): Share it with a short presentation to the mates; they must argue the following items:
 - The steps you follow to program your game.
 - Soft skills: quality of cooperation (strong and weak points).
 - What/how to improve your work.

For teachers: Each phase will have one evaluation and the final one must comprehend:

- Session 1: Observations: Behavior and quality of attention during the explanation.
- Session 2: Observations during the cooperative learning.
- Session 3: The quality of the product.
- Session 4: The quality of the presentation (how they argue, if they just read, etc.),.the quality of their self-analysis.

5. Results/Evidence

- Working game and presentation.
- e-portfolio: digital experience lab book (including photo, video...).
- Self-assessment form:

Name and Surname

SELF-ASSESSMENT FORM

I reflect on **my** behavior

	Always (or at least I tried)	Sometimes	Seldom	Never
Have I been able to work responsibly?				
Have I been able to engage?				
Did I collaborate with my partner with respect, helping him in difficulties?				
Did I collaborate politely, trying to help my partner without humiliating him for any shortcomings?				
Have I respected my partner's learning time?				
I helped my partner, without being influenced by friendships / preferences / etc.				

I reflect on **my partner's** work and behavior:

	Always (or at least I tried)	Sometimes	Seldom	Never
Was the work fruitful?				
Have we been able to engage and maintain concentration?				
Did my partner address me with politeness and respect?				
Did my partner help me when I needed it?				
Did he respect my learning time?				
Was there a positive learning atmosphere (there wasn't too much noise and we managed to maintain concentration)?				

Final Thoughts

Express a comment on the work done: explain and justify your answer:

- Do you think it was a useful training moment?
- What worked and what didn't?
- What may we do better? What should be improved?

Observations/Personal Notes

Students like this activity a lot. It's important to give them enough time to explore and to create with autonomy.

61.- Lego mindfruits (Istituto tecnico Industriale Don Luigi Orione – Fano –, Sabinianum - Monselice (PD), and Scuola Maria Ausiliatrice – Roma)

Age Average:	11-15	Teaching Hours:	14
Subjects	S T E A M	Others:	Biology
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL	PLIE SL	CL DTM IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

In this Unit Plan students will learn the:

- Organize a vegetable patch that will generate fruits and/or vegetables (ideally tomatoes if done in a sunny country).
- To Develop, build and program a sensor robot using Lego Mindstorm to evaluate the degree of ripeness of the fruits/vegetables.
- To Develop, build and program a monitoring net of sensors using micro-bit technology.

2. Materials/Resources

- Gardening tools – soil, seeds, gardening spade, watering tools, support.
- Laptop PC
- Lego Mindstorms Robot building kit and EV3 programming platform.
- Microbit programmable board with humidity sensors.

2 a) Materials/Resources - Links or references (optional)

3. Learning Objectives

- Management of a garden patch - growing plants in the full-cycle from seed to fruit.
 - Seed plant.
 - Sprout detect and handle.
 - Plant management (watering, providing support for shoots.....)

- Build and manage a monitoring station and the sensors connected to it for water and nutrient necessities.
- Program Micro:bit platform.
- Sensor knowledge and set-up.
- Basic knowledge of electronics and Ohm's law on conductivity.
- Development of a project-dedicated robot that will allow determining the growth stage of the fruits or vegetables being grown.
- Analysis of the operational environment will determine the building specifications.
- Software development of Legomindstorm robot to manage sensors.

4. Unit Plan Outline

Each session is 1 hour long:

- Session 1: Project explanation: Plant life cycle explanation. Division of students into groups.
- Session 2: Task attribution to the group members. Garden patch organization, tools, and resources required (tools and seeds already provided).
- Session 3: Ohm's law, resistance, and Micro:bit humidity sensor implementation.
- Session 4: Soil division, preparation, composting, planting, watering.
- Sessions 5/6: Robot building – challenge 1 challenge 2.
- Sessions 7/8: Programming Mindstorm and its sensors as a function of the project requirements - challenge 1 challenge 2.
- Session 9: Robot/Sensor testing (robot says “yes” or “no” depending on the color detected).
 - 12-week Project micro-management period:
 - 2 – 30min periods a week to water and check growth and fruit formation or identify issues that may be affecting the growing of the patch. Students keep a log of the activities for each session.
- Sessions 10-14: The Robot is used in the patch to determine the degree of ripeness of the fruits. When the robot says “yes” the fruit can be picked.

5. Results/Evidence

- The functionality of the sensors is built by the students.
- The functionality of the robots built by the students.
- The ripeness of the fruits selected by the robot.

Observations/Personal Notes

62.- DivInTech (La Salle La Seu d’Urgell)

Age Average:	3-16		Teaching Hours:	60		
Subjects	S	T	E	A	M	Others: Social skills and emotions
Curricular	II	EC	DG	Diversity GAP		G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL	PBL	PLIE	SL	CL	DTM IBL T Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

Introducing social robotics with students with ASD (autism spectrum disorder) and assessing its effectiveness. Through the exploration of support activities based on the interaction with robots for the education of students with special needs, we seek to improve their social and behavioral skills in a way that also has a positive impact on their evolution and academic skills.

By identifying students who meet a certain profile corresponding to the ASD dimensions (with the help of the center’s psychotherapist and based on the validation of the psychologist linked to the education consortium), particular activities adapted to each student and according to their age and ASD dimension will be programmed.

The follow-up of each case and each adapted practice will be carried out in the SIEI space (Inclusive Schooling Intensive Support, originally: “Suport Intensiu d’Escolarització Inclusiva”), a space associated with the CreaSTEAM project.

2. Materials/Resources

- NAO robot: from Softbank (www.softbankrobotics.com). It is a 57 cm tall humanoid robot with 26 degrees of freedom, which allows it to perform smooth movements. The NAO is equipped with two cameras: one in the mouth area to capture images oriented towards the earth, such as objects close to its body, and another on the head, for images from in front of the robot, as would be a person with whom it interacts. It has 7 touch sensors (head, hands, and feet), ultrasound, and inertial units to locate itself and perceive its environment. It also incorporates LEDs, microphones, and loudspeakers to communicate with people. To program it, we use the Naoqi SDK provided by Softbank, which allows us to work with it through advanced programming languages such as Python and C++. In this project, we will work with python because of its ease and speed in creating prototypes.

- iPad/Tablet.
- Nao software.
- SIEI space.

3. Learning Objectives

Initially, we will research: Exploration and discovery of opportunities where an assistive robot can support the teaching staff in educational tasks accompanying students, individually, in the consolidation of the acquisition of new knowledge and/or social skills (mainly in the case of special education); and identification of technical requirements to be able to realize the possible opportunities discovered.

- Primary
 - Emotions: The objective is to know how to identify basic emotions and go from identifying emotions in images to talking about them without visual support.
 - Reading comprehension: The objective is to understand the text they read, answer questions without reproducing the text and be able to summarize it.
 - Visual comprehension: The objective is to understand what happens in a given situation through images only when the reading level has not yet been reached.
 - Names: The objective is to learn numbers, count and write and read them.
 - Multiply: The objective is to review the multiplication tables in a non-sequential way so that it is not a simple repetition.
 - Vocabulary: The objective is to acquire vocabulary about animals, parts of the body, colors, food, school material, material to play with... in general, everyday objects.
 - High motor skills: The objective is to improve coordination with right-left movements, forward-facing, jumping, and turning...
 - Soft motor skills: The objective is to improve fine motor skills with the fingers, such as following straight lines, curves, and zig-zags...
- Secondary:
 - Emotions: The objective is to know how to identify the basic emotions, delve into the secondary ones, and identify visual experiences or situations that can be encountered.
 - Reading comprehension: The objective is to achieve reading and comprehension of a simple text.
 - Mental calculation: The objective is to get faster when performing calculations with basic operators (+ - * /), avoiding errors and acquiring tricks.
 - Geometry: The main objective is to know how to identify flat figures, then 3D figures, and, finally, to know how to relate them to real-life objects.
 - Equations: The objective is to solve the equations as they do in class, but at their own pace and with the appropriate accompaniment.
 - Social skills: The objective is to work with students in everyday situations where social skills are key (for example, knowing how to act when arriving at places, and how to ask for things...).

4. Unit Plan Outline

- Primary
 - Emotions
 - What happened?:

- Nao explains a short story with image support (sequence).
- Nao asks the student how the character feels. To answer, the student has manipulative cards with the 6 basic emotions. Once the student knows the answer, he/she shows the card corresponding to Nao.
- Rate emotions:
 - Various icons, drawings, and photographs with different emotional expressions appear on the screen.
 - The student must be able to classify them according to the emotion.
- Reading comprehension
 - Read together:
 - A text (4 lines) is displayed on the screen.
 - The student reads the text and notifies Nao when he/she has finished (by touching his/her head, for example).
 - Nao asks him what he has understood. The educator makes the evaluation.

From here on we go in parts according to what has been understood (normally they do not understand anything the first time):

 - The first sentence of the text is shown on the screen. The student reads it and tells Nao.
 - Nao asks a specific question about the sentence read.
 - The answer is evaluated.
 - Repeat the procedure with the next sentence of the text.
 - Order the sentence:
 - An unordered sentence appears on the screen.
 - The student must be able to put the sentence in order.
 - Nao will supervise this order.
 - Finally, the student reads the final sentence.
- Visual comprehension.
 - Order the images.
 - An unordered sequence of images appears on the screen.
 - The student has to order the sequence.
 - Nao asks the student to explain what is happening in the story.
 - The answer will be evaluated by the teacher.
- Names.
 - Search objects.
 - We will have the Nao with a box in front of it and several objects distributed around the class.
 - The Nao will ask the student to carry a determined number of objects, for example, to carry 6 buns.
 - The student has to look for the requested objects around the room and place them in the box.
 - Nao checks if he is doing well by counting the objects collected through the vision system.
 - After and before.

- Nao says a complex number (up to 4 digits) and asks the student to write it on the screen. For example, 1984.
- At the bottom of the screen, the numbers from 0 to 9 are displayed for the student to write the resulting figure by figure.
- Once written, Nao asks the student to write what is the number before and after the requested number, and thus practice the number sequences.
- Bingo.
 - Each child has his or her screen with a different Bingo card.
 - Nao tells the numbers.
 - Each child marks the numbers that appear on the card.
 - Nao verifies that they mark the number sung on the card. If not, he warns the corresponding student.
 - When a student does bingo, he/she will let the student know. If he/she doesn't, Nao will do it: "Look carefully at the X screen. Could it be that you have done bingo?"
- Multiply.
 - Let's paint while we multiply.
 - A relatively simple unpainted drawing appears on the screen. In each section of the drawing, there is multiplication and each number is related to color.
 - The student has to solve the multiplication of each section and paint it according to the result obtained.
 - Repeat this procedure until the drawing is correctly painted.
 - The Nao will supervise in each multiplication that the color chosen to paint is the correct one.
- Vocabulary.
 - Bubo:
 - Different vocabulary categories appear on the screen to choose which one you want to work on.
 - X objects are shown on the screen according to the chosen category, for example, animals.
 - The student has to look for them on the screen and drag and drop the card to the top of the screen to find them.
 - Search:
 - We will have the Nao with a box in front of it and several objects distributed around the class.
 - The Nao will ask the student to carry, for example, a bun.
 - The student has to look for the requested object around the room and place it inside the box when he/she finds it.
 - The Nao checks if he is doing well through the vision system.
- High motor skills.
 - Let's move the body.
 - The Nao makes different movements and the student has to imitate them. It could be done with music.
 - The movements that the Nao can do are limited: to stretch one arm, to stretch the other, to open and close the hands, to sleep, to stretch a bed...

- Evaluate how they are doing to give them indications.
- Soft motor skills.
 - Paint and draw.
 - A drawing like the following appears on the screen:

- The student has to join the names to complete the drawing.
- Nao supervises that the student follows the sequence correctly.
- Secondary:
 - Emotions.
 - What happened?
 - Show on-screen a sequence of images that explain a situation.
 - Nao asks the student to explain what happens in the cartoon (this answer must be evaluated by the teacher).
 - Once we know that the student understands what happens in the story, Nao asks him how the main character feels or which of the 6 basic emotions he identifies.
 - Show options on the screen for the student to select the answer.
 - Dice and emotions:
 - Throw a virtual card with emotion on each face (you can use the faces of the children themselves). The 6 emotions on the card are the basic emotions (happiness, sadness, sorrow, surprise, anger, and calm).
 - The student has to identify the emotion that came out.
 - Nao explains a situation and asks if it matches the emotion that came up.
 - Verbal answer YES/NO or by the screen.
 - If the answer is NO, Nao asks which of the 6 emotions is the one that is related to the situation explained.
 - The 6 emotions appear on the screen for you to answer.
 - Reading comprehension.
 - Reading together:
 - The first section of the text (5-10 lines) is displayed on the screen for the student to read (first pass).

- When he/she finishes, he/she has to warn (touching the head of the Nao, for example).
- Nao asks him what he has understood. As it is an open answer, it will be supervised by the teacher.
- The same text is shown again (second pass), and the student reads it and warns at the end.
- Nao asks questions about the text. First direct questions (as shown in the text) and then indirect questions (identify the main character, what he was doing...).
- The answers to the questions of this second pass will be asked on the screen.
- Mental calculation.
 - Find the specific pieces.
 - On the tablet, there are X-rotated fishes, and each piece will have X drawings.
 - The student throws a virtual dice to get a number.
 - The student has to spin the fish until the number that comes up on the dart is added up. Nao will keep track of the fish that are added up and ask the student the number he/she is carrying so far to verify step by step.
 - We calculate the fastest we can.
 - The Nao proposes to the student a challenge: to see how many operations he/she solves in 1 minute (for example).
 - The different operations will be shown on the screen one by one, for example, $5 * 4 + 2$.
 - At the bottom of the screen, the numbers from 0 to 9 appear so that the student can write the answer by selecting the numbers he/she needs.
 - At the end of the minute, the Nao informs what has been achieved.
- Geometry.
 - From 2D to 3D:
 - X figures are shown on the screen.
 - Nao asks the student to select one of the figures (for example the triangle).
 - The corresponding 3D figure (pyramid) is shown on the screen and Nao asks the student what it is. The answer must be entered on the screen.
 - Different images of real objects are shown on the screen and the student is asked to select the pyramid-shaped ones (in this case).
- Equations
 - Step by step:
 - A first-level equation will be displayed on the screen.
 - At the bottom of the screen appear the numbers from 0 to 9, so that the student can write the answer by selecting the numbers that he/she needs.
 - As these are equations and we are not working on mental arithmetic, the student can solve the equation in full and enter the final answer on the screen. It could also be considered to solve the equation on screen so that Nao can better follow the solution.
 - Repeat this process X times, always with first-degree equations.
- Social skills
 - What we can do now?

- A sequence of images is shown on the screen explaining a situation (for example, a child leaving home to go to school and entering the classroom).
- Nao asks the student to explain what happens in the cartoon (this answer has to be evaluated by the teacher).
- Once we know that the student understands what happens in the story, Nao asks him a question related to social skills (for example, "what will he have to do when he enters the classroom?").
- Possible options are shown on the screen (e.g., to die, to greet everyone...) so that the student can answer.

5. Results/Evidence

<https://twitter.com/LaSalleLaSeu/status/1527745527894396928?s=20&t=nt0mgylgUsckp---Kfgv8w>

<https://twitter.com/LaSalleLaSeu/status/1527304090484559873?s=20&t=nt0mgylgUsckp---Kfgv8w>

<https://twitter.com/LaSalleLaSeu/status/1526991878264180737?s=20&t=nt0mgylgUsckp---Kfgv8w>

<https://twitter.com/LaSalleLaSeu/status/1526510693675061249?s=20&t=nt0mgylgUsckp---Kfgv8w>

Observations/Personal Notes

<https://twitter.com/territorisca/status/1583420646695923713?s=20&t=nt0mgylgUsckp---Kfgy8w>

<https://pirineustv.cat/robotica-inclusiva-connecta-lleida-pirineus-18-doctubre>

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63.-Bubbo (La Salle, La Seu d’Urgell)

Age Average:	3-11	Teaching Hours:	15
Subjects	S T E A M	Others: Geography, languages, skills, and emotions	
Curricular	II EC DG	Diversity GAP	G I E R D Others:
Instruction	AL PBL PLIE SL	CL DTM IBL T	Other:

1. Short Description of the Unit Plan

Introducing social robotics with students with ASD (autism spectrum disorder) and assessing its effectiveness. Through the exploration of support activities based on the interaction with robots for the education of students with special needs, we seek to improve their social and behavioral skills in a way that also has a positive impact on their evolution and academic skills.

An activity has been designed for students with special needs to consolidate academic knowledge and social skills with the support of robotics. The design of this activity has resulted in an interactive game where a robot accompanies and motivates the student to play with a tablet application. With this game, the student works, mainly, on vocabulary acquisition, generalization of concepts, and concentration.

From the interaction between the student and the Bubbo game, the implemented system extracts the necessary information to adapt and conduct the activity accordingly. In addition, it also adapts the activity based on the student’s state (emotion, saturation, and concentration). The robot is an important part of the system, which interacts with the student giving adequate feedback for each situation and decision that is made.

2. Materials/Resources

- NAO robot.
- Facial Recognition of Microsoft Azure
- Python, and paradigm Client-Server with Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP).
- iPad / Tablet with the Bubbo game.
- SIEI space.

3. Learning Objectives

In the tablet, we find the programmed game, called Bubbo, in which different challenges to solve will appear. In front of the student and the tablet, we find Nao. This is the one in charge of following the student and adapting to the different situations. For this follow-up, several parameters are taken into account, some of them are related to the game (detection of correct exercises, detection of attempts, and detection of errors) and others are related to the Nao (recognition of the student at the beginning of the activity, detection of when he/she walks and turns, mood and cognitive status, among others).

The main learning and development objectives they had were:

- Vocabulary.
- Association of letters with concepts.
- Generalization of concepts.
- Concentration.
- Respecting the turns.
- Fine motor skills.

4. Unit Plan Outline

Vocabulary and fine motor skills: matching animals in an image:

- Level 1: This is the most basic level. It consists of three figures placed on a white background.
- Level 2: In this case increases the number of figures that appear on the screen (21 figures) on a white background.

- Level 3: Reduced number of images, specifically 10 figures, but on a contextualized background, thus working on the visual process.
- Level 4: is repeated with 12 figures and a more complex contextualized background.

- Level 5: In this level, 13 figures appear on the screen, as in the first level, but this time the piece to relate is a real image, thus working on concept generation.
- Level 6: The same function is repeated but with 21 figures.

- Level 7: From this moment on, students no longer have to relate an image but a word, thus initiating them to reading and writing.
- Level 8: The same function is repeated but with more figures, specifically 12, and a more complex contextualized background.

5. Results/Evidence

- Adapted and customized system for each student and situation.
The application resulting from the design process was Bubbo. It aims to help students with academic knowledge (such as the acquisition of vocabulary, generalization of concepts, recognition of real images, and initiation to reading) and to work on other skills such as concentration, fine motor skills, and visual processing. To play Bubbo, a board is needed, where the different configurations to start playing will appear, as shown in Figure 6.10, and the exercises and levels that the student will have to overcome. These initial configurations allow us to choose whether we will play with just one pupil or a few (thus allowing us to work on the turns) and the category we want to work on (such as animals, colors, and parts of the body).
- The same lesson is not received by all students in the same way.
- Although there are common characteristics among people with ASD, there are also many differences that depend on their personal development, the supports they may have, and whether or not they have intellectual disabilities, among others. It is for this reason that the support for people with ASD must be individualized and specialized for each case.

- If we used long sentences with all the students indistinctly, many of them would be overwhelmed and would not understand what the robot was saying. On the other hand, if we used only short sentences, the robot would be perceived by many students as repetitive and boring.
- Taking into account the profile of the users, it is also necessary that the game is not competitive or that the idea of overcoming levels appears, as their motivation is based on visual and auditory rewards, this being the main objective they have.

Observations/Personal Notes

With this unit, we wanted to study the feasibility of introducing social robotics as a support tool in schools. Both in the observation phase and the experimentation phase, it was observed that students are very interested in all technologies in general. Regarding the Bubbo game, it was noticeable that all the students had a good touch with the tablet, probably because it is a tool that is already widely used at school and home. As for the Nao robot, on the other hand, it was the first time they had contact with it. In general terms, it was received with great interest, curiosity, and excitement, which meant that the students spent more time participating in the activity than usual.

